

The logo for INSTINCT features the word "INSTINCT" in a bold, white, sans-serif font. The letter "S" is replaced by a stylized, blue, 3D-rendered shape that resembles a double helix or a pair of interlocking loops. The background of the top section is dark blue with a network of glowing white and blue nodes and lines, suggesting a digital or networked environment.

INSTINCT

D2.1

**Initial Report on Joint
Communication and Sensing
Enablers**

UNIVERSITY OF OULU

The bottom section of the cover features a dark blue background with a complex network of glowing blue nodes and lines, creating a sense of connectivity and data flow.

Executive Summary

The INSTINCT project is going to enable globally sustainable, interactive, immersive, and intelligent connectivity by developing critical new technologies for 6G networks in an integrated and innovative way. These technologies include sensing-assisted communication technologies thus allowing localization, tracking, mapping, monitoring, imaging, incident detection and semantics become integral parts of connectivity services. The project exploits the capabilities of intelligent surfaces, holographic radios and cell free systems, which offer wavefront engineering functionalities, tunability and programmability of the wireless environment and can act as reconfigurable and intelligent sensors. Furthermore, INSTINCT employs machine learning (ML) techniques and structured optimisation to incorporate the co-design of Sensing and Communications as main ingredient of multi-functional 6G network.

The work package (WP2) focuses on providing the technology enablers for the three pillars of the project, 'sense to communicate', 'communicate to sense' and 'multi-functional JCAS intelligence'. This deliverable reports the work done and initial results achieved in the WP2 during the first 10 months of the INSTINCT project.

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SEN Confidential to INSTINCT project and Commission Services

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1 Introduction

This document is the first deliverable of the work package 2 (WP2) of the INSTINCT project. It describes the initial work and results of the WP2 on enabling technologies for integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) or joint communications and sensing systems (JCAS). The WP2 targets to derive fundamental performance results and benchmarks for ISAC. The introduction of the ISAC concept in future wireless networks necessitates the development of new transceiver and network level algorithms to efficiently integrate sensing and data transmission functions. Requirements for the sensing differ significantly from the ones for communications resulting in the need for new waveform designs. The implementation of ISAC networks requires the deep understanding of baseband, radio frequency (RF) and sensing technologies, how they allow, and on the other hand, limit the achievable performance. One technology considered for the ISAC systems is the reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) that has the potential to increase the performance and range of both the data transmission and sensing. The starting point for the ISAC networks has been the case where a single transmitter and a single receiver are performing the communications and sensing functions. However, multistatic sensing can offer better performance than what can be achieved by a single receiver – transmitter pair. Furthermore, new communication network structures, such as cell free networks, will impact on how the sensing part of ISAC systems can be implemented. The WP2 of the INSTINCT project plans to address these questions. Additionally, WP2 will introduce solutions to be implemented and integrated to software (SW) and hardware (HW) demonstrations developed in WP4 (Demonstrations, Simulations and KPI/KVI Evaluations) of the project.

Use cases and applications of the sensing and data transmission will have a major impact on the technological requirements of ISAC systems. The concepts in INSTINCT project are distinguished into three categories, namely **sensing aided**, **sensing-able**, and **multi-functional and/or intelligent** systems. Use case for each of these categories with relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) have been identified in WP1 of the project and they are described in deliverable **D1.1. INSTINCT use cases definition, requirements and system architecture**. These use cases are the starting point for the work in other work packages, including WP2.

The work of WP2 is organized into three tasks. Task 2.1(T2.1), **Joint Communications and Sensing, fundamentals and algorithms**, focuses on fundamental research on ISAC theory and algorithms. We will develop methods for codesigning, optimizing and adapting dual-function waveforms for sensing and communications for mutual benefit. The task leverages on the convergence of modern multi-antenna wireless communications systems and fully adaptive multi-function MIMO radars. The developed methods stem from structured online optimization, reinforcement learning and adaptive systems, statistical inference and information theory. A key component of design, optimization, adaptation and learning in ISAC is to build and maintain awareness on the dynamic radio environment, Joint objective functions, rewards and regret models for optimization and learning will be developed. The objective functions in co-designed ISAC may be communications-centric, radar-centric or multi-objective cost aiming at pareto-optimal solutions. T2.1 will design waveforms for cooperative settings where co-designed sensing and

communications systems exchange information with communications users to create and share awareness about radio environments and interferences. This situational awareness is used as a basis for optimizing, learning and adapting the operational parameters of the ISAC system. Orthogonal designs deployed in multi-antenna and multi-carrier systems both in radar and communications are used as a starting point for waveform adaptation. The utilization of control data and network information for sensing is considered. It is also vital for synchronization needed for achieving high resolution in distributed sensing scenarios. Methods for radar sensing using communication signals (e.g. OFDM, OTFS, or DFTS-OFDM) in mono-, bi-, multistatic configurations are developed. For multistatic configurations, T2.1 will explore sensor fusion among different receivers and dealing with data association (e.g., between different surfaces with different fields of view). One part of the work is to analyse the interference in dense spectrum use scenarios, and develop new frameworks for interference avoidance and mitigation, including beamformer, precoder and decoder design and their adaptation. Algorithms for the joint operation of sensing and communications are designed to make controlled trade-off between the functionalities. The aim of this task is therefore to produce fundamental understanding of ISAC systems, their limits, and how to optimally control those. T2.1 also considers using RIS for active sensing in ISAC so that the transmitted waveforms and RIS are adapted to obtain backscattered signal that satisfy the design targets.

In T2.2, **Holographic intelligent surfaces for JCAS**, holographic surfaces are designed as a step beyond conventional antenna arrays for flexible and efficient beamforming and for the next generation RIS surfaces supporting ISAC. Electromagnetic models will be employed to characterize mathematically large RISs and holographic surfaces and to enable ISAC capabilities into them. T2.2 will study beamforming/beamtracking techniques for RIS-enabled localization and will extend this work to various MIMO techniques to obtain the algorithmic design of holographic MIMO for communications. Special focus will be put on characterizing the fundamental limits of extremely large holographic surfaces in the far-field and in the near-field for increasing the number of degrees of freedom, and on the corresponding signal processing methods for achieving the performance limits. Algorithms will be developed to provide intelligence for the network of active nodes and passive yet controllable surfaces. The aim is at auto-optimization to maximize communications and energy efficiency with human control approaching zero. As such, this task also will produce important preliminaries for WP3. The work in this task will also extend the beamforming capabilities of RISs to advanced wavefront engineering, in order to enable precise beam control for communicate-to-sense applications. Non-diffracting, focusing, and self-healing beams are studied to mitigate the increased propagation attenuation and to counteract blockage.

T2.3, **Co-design of sensing and communications**, aims at bridging the gap between the theoretical results from T2.1 and T2.2 and the practical demonstration implementations in WP4. Various HW imperfections in real transceivers and RIS surfaces are modelled. Those include, for instance, low-precision data converters and amplifier distortions. Programmable metasurfaces (low power) as a RIS are developed, and measurement and characterization results are provided for hardware-aware system design and finally for joint transmit and receive platforms. Among the transmit and receive platforms, passive beamformers will be considered as well. Different RIS

structures (including energy-harvesting ones) will be studied with scattering and sensing abilities focusing on low-power solutions. Programmable structures with different scattering characteristics based on controls will be developed and modelled via simulations. A selective set will be integrated with the HW demonstrator in WP4. The RIS will be modelled using electromagnetic simulators and equivalent simplified models representing them can be included in system or link level simulations. These models based on simulations and measurements will be embedded in collaborative algorithms with other partners. Furthermore, baseband solutions and their implementation aspects on ISAC systems are considered, for instance, how to handle the communication and sensing signals jointly at the baseband. This task is therefore closely related to demonstration implementations in WP4 and will take the lessons learned from, e.g., electromagnetic modelling of holographic surfaces in T2.2 and general system definitions developed in WP1 of the project to give the requirements to be met in the presence of non-ideal HW and baseband.

This deliverable reports the status and initial findings of the work in WP2 from the first 10 months of the project. Each section contains contributions from project partners as indicated in the list of authors table. Since the findings at this stage are initial and the work on each topic will continue, conclusions for summarizing the results are not drawn at this stage.

2 Waveforms for ISAC systems

2.1 Introduction

In this study, we evaluate two waveforms for ISAC systems within the context of 6G urban environment. Our findings indicate that, in such a dynamic setting, the primary factor which significantly influencing sensing performance is the ability to manage strong echoes reflecting off nearby objects, i.e., proximity clutter. Computer simulations reveal that Orthogonal Chirp Division Multiplexing (OCDM) outperforms Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) in this regard. Specifically, while OFDM faces challenges in detecting distant targets due to strong echoes from nearby objects, OCDM excels by accurately identifying both echoes and mitigating interference from nearby objects, thereby enabling the localization of distant targets. This study emphasizes the importance of these findings in the evolution of standards for next-generation wireless communications, particularly highlighting the crucial role of waveform selection in optimizing performance for ISAC applications in dynamic urban environments where both near and far targets coexist.

2.2 Scenario for waveform evaluation

As urban environments become increasingly complex and the demand for integrated communication and sensing systems grows, the choice of waveform will be crucial in optimizing ISAC performance. The ability to effectively manage both proximal and distant target detection in such environments is essential for the successful deployment of 6G technologies. Fig. 1 illustrates such an environment where a vehicle equipped with a ISAC platform is tasked with simultaneously detecting its surroundings and communicating with other vehicles. This scenario represents a typical 6G use case, where sensing and communication services are integrated to support as a unified service for all vehicles. The challenge in this scenario arises from the strong echoes reflected from the front car, which are so intense that they obscure the weaker echoes from the distant bike. This interference effectively blinds the ISAC node to the bike's presence. To address this issue, we propose a solution within the framework of OCDM, demonstrating that OFDM fails to mitigate these proximity echoes and is unable to detect the bike.

Figure 1. The scenario.

The received signal is first processed through a mixer, performing a Hadamard product between the received signal and the conjugate of the transmitted signal. We then propose using a bank of analog filters to mitigate the impact of proximity clutter, such as the strong reflections from the front car shown in Figure 1. This approach contrasts with the traditional use of a single filter in LFM systems. The bank of analog filters is crucial for effective clutter and cross-talk cancellation. The necessity of this approach is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows that, due to the transmission of parallel chirps, there is a periodicity in the spectrum (beat frequencies) after the mixer. This periodicity, which is not present in LFM systems, must be carefully managed. The periodic nature of the beat frequencies introduces diversity, allowing echoes from a particular target to be observed multiple times -equivalent to the number of chirp components. This repeated observation enhances target detection by reinforcing the signal of interest.

After mitigating the effects of both proximity clutter and cross-talk using a bank of analog filters, the signal -with a now reasonable dynamic range- enters the ADC. The beat signal is then processed using a FFT along the fast-time dimension to extract range information.

The second key deviation from traditional LFM processing is to remove the impact of data symbols (PSK) on the slow-time processing. If left unaddressed, these communication symbols introduce multiple frequency components, making the subsequent FFT -specifically the Doppler-FFT- unable to accurately resolve Doppler-shifts. This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 2. OCDM schematic diagram for range-Doppler processing.

Figure 3. Beat frequency plot of the OCDM in the presence of a nearby interferer. The periodic red peaks correspond to echoes from a nearby object, which must be suppressed in the analog domain (prior to ADC) using an analog filter bank.

2.3 Numerical Examples

In this section, we focus on the scenario illustrated in Figure 1 to evaluate which modulation technique is most effective at handling strong interference from nearby objects, particularly in a congested urban environment. The analysis centers on two point-targets, represented by small red squares in the range-Doppler plots. These targets correspond to the front car and the bike within the scenario of Figure 1, positioned at range indices 16 and 48, respectively, both sharing the same Doppler index of 200. This setup allows us to critically assess the ability of different modulation schemes to resolve and distinguish between these targets despite the presence of strong SI caused by proximity clutter in such a complex environment.

The simulation has been carried out for 64 subcarriers for OFDM, and a 10-bit ADC at the receiver. The yellow spot in the range-Doppler (RD) plot of Figure 4 at the coordinates (16, 200) represents the detected proximity target. Figure 4 demonstrates that OFDM is ineffective in cancelling the strong echoes of the front car, resulting in the failure of detection of the bike in the scenario. The relative amplitude of this target to the echoes reflecting off the bike is so significant that it obscures the detection of the bike.

By considering the same scenario for OQDM, the simulation has been carried out for 16 chirps with symbol length of 1024 samples and a 10-bit ADC at the receiver. Like the OFDM case, the yellow spot within the red square in the range-Doppler plot of Figure 5 represents the output of the RD processing, indicating the bike's successful detection. Figure 5 illustrates that ISAC node effectively manages the interference from the nearby target, specifically the strong echoes from the front car, allowing it to successfully detect the bike at the longer-range index of 48.

Figure 4. Range-Doppler plot of the OFDM with a nearby target, top view

Figure 5. Range-Doppler plot of the OCDM with a nearby interferer, top view.

2.4 Conclusions

This section examined the performance of two waveforms, namely OFDM and OCDM, within the context of ISAC systems operating in a 6G urban environment. The study highlights the critical challenges posed by dynamic urban settings, where the presence of strong echoes from nearby objects, referred to as proximity clutter, can severely degrade sensing performance. The analysis reveals that OCDM demonstrates superior performance compared to OFDM in addressing these challenges. While OFDM is hindered by its susceptibility to interference from proximity clutter, which compromises its ability to detect distant targets, OCDM exhibits a robust capability to not only identify but also mitigate the impact of these strong nearby echoes. This allows OCDM to accurately localize distant targets, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of the ISAC system. The findings of this research underscore the pivotal role of waveform selection in the evolution of next-generation wireless communication standards.

3 Multicarrier and Multisensor ISAC

3.1 Introduction

In ISAC, cooperation and co-design of sensing and communication are employed for mutual benefit. It allows for more efficient use of spectrum, power and HW resources. Modern radio systems are operating in highly dynamic, shared, congested or even contested spectrum. Moreover, there are a variety of sensing and communications tasks with different KPI's. These tasks require different waveforms and different use of resources such as power, time, space and frequency to guarantee or achieve the desired performance levels. ISAC takes advantage of convergence of radio frequency technologies, including parallel RF convergence, multifunction HW, shared transceiver and antenna resources, large antenna apertures, and multifunction operation and waveform diversity in radars. Hence, waveform design for ISAC must consider sharing of the transceiver HW and multiantenna resources as well. Building situational awareness about radio environment is crucial in optimizing and adapting waveforms for a particular task, radio environment and scenario. In the following we focus on multicarrier waveforms and multiantenna systems since they will be used with high probability in the emerging 6G wireless systems as well.

3.2 Multicarrier Waveforms for ISAC

The focus on Multicarrier(MC) waveforms is motivated by the fact that most current and emerging wireless communication and broadcast systems, including 4G, 5G and future 6G, WLAN/WiFi, (IEEE 802.11a), WiMAX(IEEE 802.16a), digital video broadcasting–terrestrial(DVB-T/T2)and digital audio broadcasting (DAB), employ MC waveforms that use a large number of orthogonal subcarriers [1]. Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) is the most widely used MC waveform, often accompanied by orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA) for multiuser scenarios and multiantenna-based multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technologies. Multiantenna transmissions are used in 4G systems, and 5G by leveraging massive MIMO and millimeter wave technologies. Both multiantenna systems and MC will be integral parts of the emerging 6G systems, too. The performance criteria in communications are typically considering Quality of Service (QoS) and data rate (e.g. sum rate). Knowledge of channel state information and interference levels (SINR, signal to interference and noise ratio) is typically exploited to achieve the desired performance.

Multicarrier waveforms are widely used for radar tasks, for example, the multi-carrier phase coded(MCPC) waveforms developed by Levanon, OFDM-based radar and as signals of opportunity in a variety of passive radar systems. MCPC modulates each subcarrier by a code sequence of a specific length such that after the coding is performed, the subcarriers remain orthogonal. The designed waveforms are related to multicarrier spread spectrum signals such as MC-DS-CDMA (Multicarrier Direct Sequence CDMA). The code design may consider the ambiguity function (AF)

in delay and Doppler domains in radar tasks as well as the peak to average power ratio (PAPR) for efficient use of amplifiers. Spreading provides processing gain and improves range resolution. There are a variety of radar sensing tasks such as target detection, parameter estimation, tracking, recognition, and interference and clutter mitigation. Each task has a different quantitative performance criterion, and different waveforms are needed to achieve the desired performance.

Figure 6: MCPC waveform design for multicarrier radar. A spreading code is used for each subcarriers.

Co-design of communications and sensing waveforms for mutual benefit allows for efficiently exploiting multifunction shared hardware, large aperture multi-antenna systems, convergence of RF circuit design, shared power resources and awareness of radio environment.

3.3 Online Learning for Efficient Resource Allocation in ISAC

Structured optimization and machine learning are key technologies in co-designing and jointly optimizing the performance of sensing and communication tasks in ISAC for mutual benefit [2] [3] [4]. We will consider these two different approaches for efficient co-design and resource allocation in ISAC. The design problem may be radar-centric, communications-centric, or multi-objective joint design with appropriate weights for sensing and communications objectives. Structured optimization requires accurate information on the model, operational environment, parameters and constraints of the ISAC system to formulate an objective function with a number of constraints. The resulting problem may not be convex. Solving a large and non-convex multi-objective optimization problem requires typically substantial computational resources and plenty of time in a very dynamic environment. Solving structured optimization problems is usually done in a batch mode, and there is no learning from past experiences involved. In addition, there may be a substantial modeling deficit that can be addressed via data-driven machine or statistical learning. Moreover, the nature of the problem and its constraints do not lend themselves to commonly used optimization tools or algorithms. Machine learning may provide algorithms to solve such problems.

We consider these two different approaches for efficient waveform co-design, optimization and resource allocation in ISAC. The developed methods sense the radio environment, build awareness state of the dynamic spectrum including channel and interference statistics as a function of location and frequency, propagation environment, target scenarios. The awareness

combined with sensing and communications task objectives is then used to optimize and learn the waveforms and resource allocations of an ISAC system. Reinforcement Learning (RL) provides a powerful framework for closed loop optimization of the waveforms and resources. Model-based RL allows for faster convergence, avoids unnecessary trial and error steps in learning, and makes the learning more transparent and interpretable. Moreover, it connects the learning with control theory so that stability of the RL system can be studied.

We have focused on allocating MC frequency resources, namely subcarriers and resource blocks of a MC ISAC system to achieve the required performance levels in multiuser communications and various sensing tasks. Mutual Information (MI) based criteria are used as reward functions, and the models how channels and interferences evolve are learned from observed data. Markov Decision Process (MDP) and Partially Observable MDP models are employed. We have demonstrated that the regret (cost of learning) is decidedly sublinear. A bound for regret has been established using analytical tools.

3.3.1 Beamspace processing

There is an ongoing convergence of wireless communications and radio frequency systems, especially in terms of using large aperture antenna arrays both in advanced radar systems and 5G and 6G wireless. Spatial processing is a crucial capability in densely used radio spectrum. In wireless communications, spatial processing means typically beamforming by steering a high gain towards desired users and attenuating interferences from non-cooperative users. In radar sensing, the desired beampatterns may be significantly more complicated and diverse depending on the sensing tasks at hand (target search and detection, target parameter estimation, imaging, focusing, and tracking for example). Beamspace processing allows for combining the benefits of phased array and MIMO processing. Beamspace processing changes the spatial model from the element space to orthogonal beamspace in which the beams can be allocated to different tasks similarly to subcarriers in frequency domain without causing interference to neighboring beams.

Fig. DFT beams with 10 antenna elements.

Figure 7: Orthogonal beams produced by beamspace transform. Beams are allocated to sensing and communications tasks using RL.

Beam allocation and beam alignment is based on information theoretic criteria such as MI and awareness of channels and interferences. Waveform design and optimization may be done jointly

in spatial and frequency domains by allocating beams and resource blocks (subcarriers) to different sensing and communications tasks using RL methods. Methods based on Bayesian Thompson Sampling have been developed and their performance studied [5].

3.4 Resource-Efficient MIMO ISAC System Design

The research outlined in this section will explore the theme “*doing more with less*” in emerging multi-sensor ISAC systems via the efficient use of space, time and frequency resources. A core question that is explored is which sensor array geometries, transmit waveforms, or receiver (beamforming) architectures can achieve a desired level of sensing and communications performance using the fewest possible resources? In the context of sensing, *sparse sensor arrays* have recently been shown to be able to significantly improve identifiability, enhance resolution, and reduce costs compared to conventional uniform geometries by reducing the number of sensors and related expensive and power-hungry analog/digital circuitry [6]. An enabler of these benefits is leveraging so-called *array redundancy*, a form of spatial repetition of virtual phase centers (of transmit-receiver sensor pairs) that naturally emerges in sensing and imaging problems employing multiple (phase-coherent) sensors. Figure 8 illustrates a sparse array geometry and corresponding redundancy of the virtual sensors in the context of ISAC. While some sensing-centric advantages of array redundancy have recently been explored, such as robustness to sensor failure [7] and faster imaging [8], key questions remain unanswered regarding how to fully harness it in ISAC. This work will attempt fill this gap by judiciously leveraging sparse arrays, and the latent, underutilized resource of array redundancy to provide ISAC performance gains while facilitating more resource-efficient, low-cost and robust multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems.

After briefly introducing the signal model and key performance indicators in section 3.4.1, section 3.4.2 introduces the core principle of “array-informed” system design which is essential for resource-efficient MIMO system. In practice, this involves tailoring the probing waveforms and beamforming architecture to the deployed array geometry, such that any array redundancy is maximally leveraged. Section 3.4.3 concludes the discussion by outlining an ISAC-specific application of this general array-informed principle. Specifically, information is encoded into transmit sensor subsets in a manner that provides flexibility in codebook design for communications, while guaranteeing a desired level of sensing performance.

Figure 8: Monostatic ISAC system actively sensing its environment and serving a mobile user. The physical Tx and (sparse) Rx arrays give rise to a set of virtual Tx-Rx antenna pairs, which may overlap. This overlap is known as array redundancy

3.4.1 ISAC MIMO signal model and key performance indicators

Next, we briefly outline a basic MIMO ISAC model to make the subsequent discussion more concrete. We consider an ISAC base station (BS), with N_t transmit (Tx) antennas collocated with N_r receive (Rx) antennas. The array geometries are assumed linear for simplicity. The BS both senses the environment in a monostatic fashion and communicates with one or several multi-antenna users (UEs). The discrete-time transmitted ISAC waveform is represented by spatio-temporal matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times T}$, where T denotes the number of time samples or coherence block length. The general objective of the ISAC system is to design this waveform matrix to simultaneously fulfil both the sensing and communications goals; discussed next.

The downlink received signal at i th UE with M_i antennas is represented by

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{W}_i,$$

where $\mathbf{H}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{M_i \times N_t}$ is the channel matrix between the BS and i th UE and $\mathbf{W}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{M_i \times T}$ is a noise/interference matrix. The communications task of the BS is to transmit information to the UEs—reliably and at a high rate—by designing the set from which \mathbf{S} is drawn; the so-called “codebook”. The task of the i th UE is to decode its message in \mathbf{S} given measurement \mathbf{Z}_i and, possibly, channel \mathbf{H}_i or an estimate thereof. Key performance indicators (KPIs) considered in this work will include achievable rate and minimum codeword distance, which impact the bit error rate at the UEs.

Waveform matrix \mathbf{S} is also used for sensing at the BS. Assuming K far field scatterers (in the same delay-Doppler cell) with angular directions $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]^K$ and scattering coefficients $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \in \mathbb{C}^K$ the backscattered signal observed at the BS assumes the form

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{A}_r(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}) \mathbf{A}_t^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{N},$$

where $\mathbf{A}_r(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times K}$ and $\mathbf{A}_t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times K}$ denote the manifolds of the Rx and Tx arrays, respectively, and $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times T}$ is a noise/interference matrix. The sensing task of the BS is to estimate $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ given measurement \mathbf{Y} , waveform matrix \mathbf{S} , and knowledge of the array manifold functions $\mathbf{A}_r(\cdot)$, $\mathbf{A}_t(\cdot)$. Considered sensing KPIs will include identifiability and resolution. These

fundamental KPIs characterize, respectively, the existence of a unique mapping from unknown parameters θ to measurements \mathbf{Y} ; and how well the system can discriminate between closely spaced targets (small differences between the elements of vector θ) in the presence of noise or interference.

3.4.2 Low-rank waveforms and hybrid beamforming informed by array geometry

Recently, an intriguing link has been explored between array redundancy and the efficient use of transmit waveforms in sensing: waveform design should be cognizant of the array geometry if the goal is to maximize identifiability using the fewest independent waveforms [9]. This corresponds to low-rank waveform matrices \mathbf{S} , where $\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t$. In ISAC, it may be desirable to deploy such low-rank waveforms because of rank-deficient communications channels \mathbf{H}_i , a need to boost SNR via transmit beamforming, a limited transmission time T , or because of hardware constraints, such as a limited number of Tx/Rx front ends. Transmitting fewer independent streams is also natural when the number of antennas per user at the BS is large, as in modern 5G communications systems.

Low-rank waveforms can be viewed as a form of *compression* at the transmitter. This viewpoint raises the possibility of a general “array-informed” compression framework that also includes various partially analog—or so-called hybrid beamforming—receiver architectures, which become increasingly relevant at higher operating frequencies where fully digital solutions become impractical. Figure 9 illustrates the general architecture of such a compressive MIMO system. The ramifications of array-informed compression in sensing systems are yet to be fully understood. This includes characterizing which (redundant) array geometries admit lossless compression such that reducing the number of independent waveforms or Rx front ends does not hamper identifiability or resolution. Answering this and other related questions requires mathematically investigating the so-called Kruskal rank and smallest restricted singular value of key system matrices with rich structure induced by the employed spatial sampling geometry, waveforms, and receiver architecture. Doing so will yield new insight into designing high-performance resource-efficient multisensory systems for ISAC that achieve enhanced resolution and identifiability at low cost and power consumption.

Figure 9. General architecture of MIMO BS. Employing a waveform of reduced rank or fewer Tx/Rx front ends than antennas (so-called analog or hybrid beamforming) lead to a compressive measurement model. The question is under which circumstances is this compression “lossless” for the task at hand, such as parameter estimation.

3.4.3 Sensing guarantees for index modulation-based ISAC via transmit sensor selection

A practical communications scheme that has recently gained significant research in ISAC is *index modulation* (IM) [10]. The core idea of IM is to embed information in quantities such as transmit antenna selections [11], the association between the transmitted waveforms and antennas [12], or subcarrier indices of the transmitted waveform(s) [10]. Among the advantages of IM in ISAC is that certain modulated quantities can be transparent to the sensing functionality. For example, a MIMO radar transmitting orthogonal waveforms would be invariant to permutations of the waveforms among the transmit antennas. However, this permutation could still convey information to a communications receiver, which might know the waveforms *a priori*, but not which transmit antennas they originated from. Different IM modulation techniques may naturally be combined to improve the overall rate of the system, typically at the expense of an increased decoding complexity.

Herein, we will apply the previously learned lessons from resource-efficient MIMO system design to the diverse applications of *transmit antenna subset selection in ISAC, including IM*. In the context of MIMO communications, IM via antenna selection is also known as *generalized spatial modulation* [13]. Note that sensor selection promotes resource-efficiency (reducing cost and power consumption), as fewer front ends than antennas need to be employed. In the case of transmit antenna selection, the codebook \mathcal{C} used for communications consists of transmit subarrays. A key challenge is then to design this codebook to ensure a certain level of performance for both communications and sensing functionalities. Note that given a transmit array with N_t antennas, there are $|\mathcal{C}| \leq \binom{N_t}{Q}$ possible subarrays with Q antennas. From a communications perspective, using all these subsets would be desirable for maximizing the achievable rate at high SNR. From a sensing perspective, however, all codewords may not be equally desirable. For example, some subsets may yield unsatisfactory performance in terms of the Tx or joint Tx-Rx beampattern [11]. The question thus arises: How large can the codebook $|\mathcal{C}|$ be to meet a desired level of sensing performance? Furthermore, how should \mathcal{C} (the subsets of Tx sensors) be chosen? We will explore these questions by focusing on identifiability as a sensing KPI. It is well-known that the number of targets that can be uniquely identified by a collocated

active sensing system depends on the so-called *sum co-array*—a virtual array model consisting of the set of sums between pairs of Tx-Rx antenna positions. Hence, identifiability guarantees for IM can be provided by ensuring that each Tx subarray in \mathcal{C} , when paired with an appropriately designed Rx array, yields a desired (typically, uniform) sum co-array. A key research problem within this context that will be investigated is the trade-off between the number of identifiable targets and the size the of \mathcal{C} , or the minimum distance (in a suitable sense) between the codewords in \mathcal{C} . This is expected to reveal insight into the fundamentally achievable sensing and communications performance in MIMO ISAC systems employing sensor-selection-based IM.

4 Emerging Solutions to Positioning Challenges

4.1 Overview of Positioning Challenges and Emerging Solutions

Traditionally, location-based services have relied on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) for positioning. GNSS determines the position of user equipment (UE) through multilateration, using range measurements from multiple satellites. However, this method is subject to several limitations, including ionospheric and tropospheric disturbances, multipath interference, clock inaccuracies, and loss of satellite visibility. As a result, GNSS-only positioning typically achieves meter-level accuracy, which is insufficient for many emerging applications [14].

With the growing demand for advanced localization in applications such as smart cities, public safety systems, smart factories, and autonomous vehicles, more stringent accuracy requirements have emerged. Among these, the intelligent mobility sector is particularly critical. Autonomous vehicles offer potential solutions to address modern urban challenges such as road safety, traffic congestion, and pollution, but these require highly accurate positioning systems to function reliably [15].

4.2 The Role of 5G in Enhancing Positioning Accuracy

Cellular networks, with their extensive coverage, offer a promising solution to overcome the limitations of GNSS. While earlier cellular technologies provided coarse positioning (e.g., cell-level accuracy [16]), the advent of 5G New Radio (5G-NR) has significantly improved positioning precision. With 5G-NR, advancements such as higher temporal resolution and large antenna arrays enable more accurate estimations of time-of-flight (ToF) and direction of arrival, allowing for enhanced positioning capabilities [17].

4.3 Introducing 5GNSS: A Hybrid Localization Framework

We focus on a novel hybrid localization solution, termed 5GNSS (cf., Figure 10), which integrates ranging measurements from both 5G-NR and GNSS. By combining these two technologies, 5GNSS offers superior accuracy compared to standalone GNSS or 5G-NR systems. While our primary focus is on vehicular applications, the benefits of this approach extend to other use cases requiring high localization accuracy and reliability.

Figure 10. Proposed 5GNSS framework for the fusion of GNSS and 5G-NR localization systems (reproduced from [18])

The 5GNSS framework is designed with flexibility in mind, allowing for the potential inclusion of additional data sources in the future. It also facilitates widespread commercial adoption by leveraging existing technologies and enabling retrofitting to current infrastructure. This ensures a scalable solution that can meet the evolving demands of both current and future positioning applications.

4.4 Review of State-of-the-Art Positioning Solutions

Current positioning solutions employ various techniques to mitigate the performance limitations of GNSS in challenging environments. These typically combine GNSS measurements with data from cellular networks, inertial sensors, or other sensor types. In this section, we review the most relevant solutions proposed to date and compare them with the 5GNSS approach.

Several studies have explored the potential of 4G LTE to improve localization, either as a standalone system or in conjunction with GNSS [19], [20], [21], [22]. These works leverage time-difference-of-arrival and roundtrip time measurements, often using Kalman or other filtering techniques to fuse data with GNSS. Similar to our approach, these methods estimate range based on reference signal observations. However, our proposed solution utilizes 5G-NR instead of LTE, benefiting from the higher temporal resolution of 5G.

The hybridization of GNSS with 5G-NR has been explored in various studies, which can be categorized into three groups: theoretical models [23], [24], point positioning methods [25], [26], and temporal-filtering-based approaches [27], [28]. In contrast to these solutions, 5GNSS simplifies the approach by avoiding complex filtering methods, such as extended Kalman Filters, and instead capitalizes on the different sampling rates of the two systems using standard signal processing techniques.

Other studies have investigated the integration of GNSS with inertial sensors, inertial measurement units, and 3D digital maps [29], [30], [31]. Unlike these solutions, 5GNSS does not depend on sensor data or detailed digital maps, which may not always be available. However, when such resources are accessible, they could be used to further enhance 5GNSS accuracy.

A computer-vision-based approach, which combines single or stereo cameras with inertial sensors, has also been proposed in e.g., [32], [33], [34]. While this method offers promising accuracy, it encounters limitations in poor lighting or adverse weather conditions. In comparison, 5GNSS remains effective under such conditions, making it a complementary solution to vision-based systems.

Finally, the use of RADAR and LiDAR sensors for autonomous driving has been explored in e.g., [35], [36], [37]. While these systems demonstrate high performance and robustness in diverse environments, they rely on expensive equipment that is not widely available in most vehicles. In contrast, 5GNSS leverages GNSS and 5G technology—both of which are expected to be widely deployed—offering a cost-effective, scalable solution that is suitable for the mass market and can be retrofitted for assisted or automated driving, as well as other applications.

4.5 Multilateration in Positioning Systems

Most positioning systems, including GNSS, determine location by performing multilateration. In a 2D positioning context, we consider a 2D map where $p_n = (x_n, y_n)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$ represents the known positions of N nodes. The goal is to estimate the unknown position $p = (x, y)$ of a UE. The distance (or range) between the UE and the n -th node is given by the equation $d_n = \tau_n c = \|p_n - p\|$, where c is the speed of light, τ_n is the ToF, and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean distance. In positioning applications, the system relies on a reference time. However, since the clocks of the UE and the nodes are generally not synchronized with the system time, the measured distances are affected by an unknown clock bias in addition to noise-related errors. Assuming node synchronization errors are known and compensated for, once at least four distance measurements d_n are collected, the UE can estimate both its position and its clock bias using multilateration:

$$\delta t_{UE}, \hat{p} = \arg \min \|d - \hat{d}\|^2,$$

where d and \hat{d} represent the actual and estimated distance vectors between the N nodes and the UE, respectively, and δt_{UE} is the clock error of the UE.

Each of the N distance estimations corresponds to a circle centered at the respective node, with a radius \hat{d}_n . Due to errors from noise and other distortions, these circles do not intersect at a single point, but rather define an area. To solve this, a nonlinear least-squares (NLLS) estimation method is applied. NLLS linearizes the quadratic form using a Taylor expansion, rearranging the gradient equations into a set of linear equations, which are then solved iteratively using algorithms such as Gauss-Newton [38].

The effectiveness of multilateration is influenced by the number, quality, and geometric arrangement of the measurements. This relationship is quantified by the Horizontal Dilution of Precision (HDOP), which measures how errors in distance estimations and the spatial configuration of nodes impact the accuracy of positioning on the horizontal plane.

4.6 Overview of GNSS and Signal Blockage Impacts

GNSS provides positioning solutions to UE via signals emitted by orbiting satellites. Several GNSS systems ensure global coverage, with the NAVSTAR Global Positioning System (GPS) being the most widely used. A typical GNSS includes a constellation of satellites, but due to signal blockage, only a subset of these satellites may be visible to the UE at any given time. This visibility is influenced by the UE's elevation mask, which defines the minimum elevation angle at which satellites are visible. The elevation of a satellite is the angle between the Earth's surface and the LoS to the satellite. The elevation mask depends largely on the ratio of building height to street width, making signal blockage more significant in dense urban environments, where tall buildings reduce the visibility of low-elevation satellites.

Each visible satellite broadcasts a signal containing a ranging code and a data message. The ranging code indicates the transmission time, while the data message provides information about the satellite's orbit. The UE uses these signals to compute its position and time solution at a rate of up to 10 Hz. This positioning is performed through multilateration, which calculates the distance between the UE and each visible satellite based on the ToF of the received signals.

Ideally, if the clocks of both the UE and the satellites were perfectly synchronized, the distance between the UE and a satellite could be directly determined by multiplying the ToF by the speed of light. However, in practice, synchronization errors between the clocks introduce biases in the measured distances, along with atmospheric effects that perturb the signal's speed and direction. This leads to the concept of a "pseudorange", which includes both the true range and an error term caused by the lack of synchronization.

The satellite clock errors are transmitted in the data message, allowing the UE to correct them. However, the clock error of the UE remains unknown and must be estimated as part of the positioning process. After compensating for satellite clock errors, the UE can measure a corrected pseudorange, which reflects both the actual distance to the satellite and the clock bias of the UE. The UE's speed can then be derived from the rate of change of this pseudorange over time.

4.7 5G-NR ToF Estimation

The 5G-NR standard incorporates several types of reference signals, which can be dynamically allocated within each time slot, allowing for adaptability in sample rate R_{5G-NR} . While many of these signals are suitable for positioning, the Positioning Reference Signal (PRS) is commonly used. However, two key factors affect the performance of PRS for localization: hearability and resource element density. Hearability limits how many nodes (gNBs, as per 3GPP terminology) a UE can receive simultaneously through the same reference signal. Resource element density affects the bandwidth of the reference signal, which in turn impacts the accuracy of range estimations.

The ToF can be estimated using a maximum likelihood (ML) approach, which involves searching for the peak in the circular cross-correlation between transmitted and received reference signals [39]. Typically, these reference signals are designed using sequences from the constant

amplitude zero autocorrelation (CAZAC) family, which possess the zero autocorrelation property: $R_{\xi\xi}(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \xi(n)\xi^*(n+q) = \delta(q)$, where ξ is the reference signal sequence, ξ^* is its complex conjugate, N is the sequence length, and q is the delay.

In practice, the transmitted and received reference signals, u and v , are transformed into their frequency-domain equivalents. The circular correlation between the signals is computed by multiplying one signal with the complex conjugate of the other in the frequency domain. The ToF is then estimated by finding the peak of this circular cross-correlation, and the distance between a gNB and the UE can be determined by multiplying the ToF by the speed of light. This process involves significant complexity and requires full knowledge of the reference signal, which can be challenging when the signal is interspersed with payload data. More efficient approximations of the ML solution, such as the Fitz Estimator, can reduce computational complexity [40].

4.8 5GNSS Concept and Design

The 5GNSS system (cf., Figure 11) is a hybrid approach that fuses distance measurements from both 5G-NR and GNSS, aiming to surpass the performance of standalone systems. The system operates by collecting distance estimates at rates R_{GNSS} and $R_{\text{5G-NR}}$, where typically $R_{\text{5G-NR}} > R_{\text{GNSS}}$, leading to $F = \lceil R_{\text{5G-NR}} / R_{\text{GNSS}} \rceil$ as the number of samples from 5G-NR over a single GNSS interval.

4.8.1 Measurement Preprocessing

In the preprocessing stage, noisy and NLoS measurements are removed to enhance the reliability of distance estimates. The system filters out measurements from gNBs with SNR values below a threshold and removes outliers using statistical methods, resulting in a cleaner set of distance measurements.

4.8.2 Oversampling and Smoothing

Due to data filtering, not every gNB produces exactly F measurements in a GNSS interval. To address this, oversampling is applied to interpolate additional samples. An exponential weighted moving average (EWMA) filter is then used to smooth the oversampled data, helping to improve accuracy by adjusting based on the UE speed.

4.8.3 Rate Matching

Synchronization between 5G-NR and GNSS is essential for the fusion process. To match the rates of both systems, the rate-matching block selects the most reliable 5G-NR sample from the set of oversampled data, ensuring the data from both systems can be effectively fused.

4.8.4 Fusion and Position Estimation

Once synchronized measurements are available at the GNSS rate, the system assigns weights to the 5G-NR and GNSS data, allowing the more reliable system to have a greater influence on the final positioning estimate. These weighted measurements are combined and used to compute

the UE's position through multilateration, solved via the NLLS approach, initialized using 5G-NR data due to its lower latency.

Figure 11. Details on the fusion of 5G-NR and GNSS samples (reproduced [18][18])

5 RIS for Range-Angle Localization

Wireless communications have been so far operating in the far-field of the radiating elements. With the incorporation of RISs, the near-to-far-field transition can be engineered via the footprint size and, therefore, new techniques that can take advantage of this ability can be implemented. In this section we explain how the RIS can be used to enable new functionalities beyond conventional beamforming, such as beam-focusing. Leveraging the beamforming and beam-focusing capabilities, we present the concept of hierarchical RIS-assisted, range-angle localization.

5.1 From Full to Partial Illumination

It is well known that the waves radiated by antennas evolve into the far-field roughly at the Fraunhofer distance, [41] [42]. For conventional antennas, e.g. phased arrays, the size of the radiating element (or radiating aperture) extends from a fraction of a wavelength up to only a few wavelengths and, therefore, the radiated waves quickly enter the far-field. With RISs, though, this intuitive picture can change. Owing to their large surface, usually extending up to several wavelengths, waves reflected by the RIS may evolve under a new aperture, i.e. an *effective RIS aperture*, associated with a new Fraunhofer distance.

In Figure 12(a) a RIS-aided link is illustrated, where the Access Point (AP) illuminates the RIS with a beam of tunable-width, associated with the AP gain (G_{AP}). For relatively low G_{AP} , the AP beam illuminates the entire RIS and, therefore, the RIS captures only a part of the incident beam. As a result, the footprint of the reflected beam does not depend on the AP beam width, rather is determined by the actual area of the RIS. Hence, the effective aperture of the RIS is determined by the finite area of the RIS; we refer to this case as *finite RIS regime* or *full illumination regime*. In the opposite extreme where G_{AP} is relatively high, the AP beam illuminates only a portion of the RIS and, therefore, the RIS captures the entire incident beam. As a result, the width of the reflected beam on the RIS is defined entirely by the AP beam footprint, i.e. the actual RIS size does not matter. In this case the RIS acquires an effective aperture, which is determined by the AP beam footprint. In essence, the AP beam “sees” an effectively infinite RIS and we refer to this case as *infinite RIS regime* or *partial illumination regime*. The transition from full to partial illumination can be achieved either with illuminating a RIS with an AP beam of increasing gain or, alternatively, with increasing RIS size under constant AP gain, as depicted in Figure 12(b).

The size of the effective RIS aperture plays a decisive role on the overall performance of the RIS-aided link and, therefore, the trade-off between the RIS size, AP beam-width and AP power density, can lead to a rich performance with respect to the power received by the UE. For example, for an AP beam of constant power and variable gain, increasing the AP gain does not increase the received power indefinitely. As was shown in [43], the received power acquires a maximum that occurs when the effective RIS aperture is such that the user location coincides with the distance marking the transition from the near-field to the far-field of the beam, as shown in Figure 12(c).

Figure 12. RIS illumination regimes. (a) The AP illuminates the RIS with a beam of tunable width/gain. (b) Effect of finite RIS size on the AP power captured by the RIS. For small RIS size the RIS is fully illuminated, capturing only a small fraction of the AP beam power. As the RIS size increases, the RIS becomes partially illuminated, capturing the entire AP beam. (c) Received power at the UE, as a function of the AP gain (reproduced from [43]).

5.2 Wavefront Engineering with RISs

The size of the effective RIS aperture determines the Fraunhofer distance, i.e. the transition from the near- to the far-field of the beam. For small aperture, the Fraunhofer distance is brought close to the RIS, and the reflected beam quickly enters its far-field. This case corresponds to conventional *beamforming*. For larger aperture, however, the Fraunhofer distance is pushed far from the RIS, and this flexibility to adjust the Fraunhofer distance can enable new functionalities beyond conventional beamforming, such as *beam-focusing*. Both operations can be advantageous to a number of applications, including but not limited to beam-tracking, blockage avoidance and power transfer. To achieve such beam profiles, the RIS transforms the incident beam into a reflected beam with tailored properties, by properly phase shifting the incident wave.

To describe the necessary phase shifts for both operations, let us consider a RIS that resides on the xy plane and steers beams on the xz plane. The E-field of the AP beam that is incident on the RIS can be written as

$$E_i(x, y) = E_0(x, y) \exp(jk \sin \theta_i x)$$

where $E_0(x, y)$ is the real-valued amplitude, θ_i is the angle of incidence and k is the free-space wavenumber. To form a beam with the desired profile, the RIS transforms the incident beam by, first, correcting the tilt of the incident beam [performed by the $\exp(jk \sin \theta_i x)$ term] and, subsequently, introducing a phase φ with tailored functional form, to shape a reflected beam with desired characteristics [44]. Mathematically, this operation is expressed as

$$E_r(x, y) = E_i(x, y) \exp(-jk \sin \theta_i x) \exp(j\varphi) = E_0(x, y) \exp(j\varphi)$$

i.e. the incident beam's footprint on the RIS, E_0 , is reshaped according to the phase term prescribed by the phase φ . Depending on the functional form of φ , different beams can be generated, as we will demonstrate next.

5.2.1 RIS-aided beamforming

Beam-forming is the most fundamental of the functionalities of RISs [45] and is typically used to steer the incident beam towards the desired direction. An example of a numerically propagated beam that is steered at angle θ_r is shown in Figure 13(a), left panel. Beam-steering is achieved by imposing linear phase shifts on the RIS elements, i.e.

$$\varphi = k \sin \theta_r x$$

where k is the free-space wavenumber, θ_r is the angle of reflection on the steering plane.

Beamforming with an RIS can be used to increase the received power at the direction of the user, establish an additional LoS link, or track the user. The width of the reflected beam depends on the effective RIS aperture, i.e. the size of the AP footprint of the incident beam on the RIS or the size of the RIS, whichever is smaller. Controlling the near-to-far-field transition distance is fundamental as the optimization of beamforming in terms of received power depends on it. As shown in [43], maximizing the received power at a certain distance requires a specific RIS size or footprint that sets the Fraunhofer distance at the RIS-UE distance, i.e. that effectively places the UE at the near-to-far-field transition of the RIS. Moreover, under partial illumination (in this case the near-to-the-far-field transition is determined by the Rayleigh distance), the beam in its near-field undergoes negligible diffraction, essentially propagating with constant peak power, which is ideal for power transfer applications [46]. The beam power is maximum along the beam center, and the spatial locations with half-maximum (or 3dB) power mark a cone with apex angle $\Delta\theta$, which determines the angular beam-width. The beam-width depends on the incident beam footprint and, the larger the footprint on the RIS, the smaller the beam-width and, consequently, the higher the resolution in localization-related applications. This is shown schematically in Figure 13(b), left panel.

5.2.2 RIS-aided, near-field beam-focusing

Beam-focusing is the ability of a RIS to focus the power of the reflected beam to a small area, similarly to how a lens focuses light onto a focal point. An example of a numerically propagated beam is shown in Figure 13(b), right panel. Beam-focusing can be achieved simply by imposing a parabolic phase profile on the RIS elements [47], i.e. of the form

$$\varphi = -\frac{kr^2}{2f_0}$$

where f_0 is the focal distance, and r is the distance of each element from the center of the RIS.

Beam-focusing can be used to estimate the location of the UE, to maximize the received power, as well as for wireless power transfer applications. The power is maximized at the focal point, and the locus of the spatial locations with half-maximum (or 3dB) power marks an ellipsoid centered at the focal point and oriented with its major axis along the beam propagation direction. Its size depends on the incident beam footprint, as well as the RIS-focal point distance (focal distance). In principle, the larger the footprint on the RIS, the smaller the size of the 3dB ellipsoid and, consequently, the higher the resolution in localization-related applications and the higher the maximum power at the focal point. This is shown schematically in Figure 13(b), right panel.

(a) Beam propagation

(b) Schematic representation

Figure 13. Beam-forming and beam-focusing with a RIS. (a) Numerical propagation and (b) schematic representation of both beam types. The shaded areas in (b) mark the beam area contained within the 3dB width for beamforming and the 3dB range for beam-focusing.

5.2.3 Beamforming and beam-focusing efficiency

There are several parameters that determine how efficiently beam-forming and beam-focusing can be realized. For example, the size of the AP's beam's footprint on the RIS, the steering angle and the focal distance are parameters that control the power density distribution in space and, hence, have direct impact on the efficiency of beam formation.

To study the efficiency of beam formation, the footprint of the incident beam on the RIS is modeled by a Gaussian distribution [43], [47], which is a good approximation to the functional form of the beam's main lobe, for most practical cases. Without loss of generality, we the beam is y -polarized and propagates on the xz -plane, the E-field of which at $z = 0$ is written as

$$\mathbf{E}_i(x, y) = E_0 \exp\left[-\frac{(x \cos \theta_i)^2 + y^2}{w_{RIS}^2}\right] \exp(-jk \sin \theta_i x) \hat{\mathbf{y}}$$

where E_0 is a complex constant and w_{RIS} is the radius of the footprint at normal incidence ($\theta_i = 0$). This model takes into account the fact that under oblique incidence ($\theta_i \neq 0$) the footprint acquires elliptical shape, with the major axis of the ellipse residing on the x -axis. The field that is reflected by the RIS on the xz -plane is associated with the power density $S_r = |E_r|^2 / 2Z_0$ given by [47]

$$S_r(x, z) = \frac{2P_t \cos \theta_i}{\pi w_{RIS}^2} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{z_R \cos \theta_r}\right)^2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{z_R \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{\cos \theta_r}\right)^4}} \exp\left[-\frac{2(x \cos \theta_r - z \sin \theta_r)^2}{w_{RIS}^2 \left(\left(\frac{\cos \theta_r}{\cos \theta_i} - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z \cos \theta_i}{z_R \cos^2 \theta_r}\right)^2\right)}\right],$$

Where P_t is the total beam power, Z_0 is the free-space wave impedance and $z_R = \pi w_{RIS}^2 / \lambda$ is the Rayleigh length. The parameter $|R| < 1$ is the amplitude of the RIS reflection coefficient and accounts for possible losses at the RIS surface. For a lossless RIS, $|R| = 1$.

As an example, let us consider a D-band indoor scenario with operation frequency of 150 GHz. The RIS is lossless ($|R| = 1$) and is able to perform both beamforming and beam-focusing, as depicted

in Figure 14(a). The AP is equipped with a directional antenna of tunable gain that transmits a beam of constant power $P_t = 1\text{ W}$ towards the RIS. Depending on the distance d_{AP} and orientation θ_{AP} of the AP relative to the RIS, footprints of different size and ellipticity are captured by the RIS, all with the same total power. Despite the fact that the total beam power is constant, the beam dynamics change when the AP location changes, with direct consequences on the power received by a UE that is targeted by the beam. The power density along the beam center for several such cases is shown in Figure 14(b) for fixed AP orientation ($\theta_{AP} = 30^\circ$) and in Figure 14(c) for fixed AP distance ($d_{AP} = 2\text{ m}$). In all these examples the RIS steering angle is $\theta_r = 60^\circ$. The observed performance is associated with the size of the AP beam footprint on the RIS, w_{RIS} , which is controlled indirectly via d_{AP} and θ_{AP} : increasing d_{AP} and/or θ_{AP} leads to larger footprint w_{RIS} , bringing the beam into its near-field. In case of beamforming, this leads to beam propagation with reduced, however practically constant, peak power. The power density reduces with increasing w_{RIS} , as a result of power conservation (the total beam power is preserved). In case of beam-focusing, a larger footprint brings the beam deeper into its near-field, enabling better focusing, and increasing its power density at the focal point.

Figure 14. Impact of AP distance and orientation with respect to the RIS, on beamforming (top row panels) and beam-focusing (bottom row panels). (a) Schematic representation of RIS-aided beamforming and beam-focusing. (b) Power density along the beam center, for AP locations characterized by $\theta_{AP} = 30^\circ$ and $d_{AP} = 1, 2, 3\text{ m}$. (c) Power density along the beam center, for AP locations characterized by $d_{AP} = 2\text{ m}$ and $\theta_{AP} = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ$. In all examples the beam has total power $P_t = 1\text{ W}$, and the RIS steers the beam along the direction characterized by $\theta_r = 60^\circ$. For beam-forming $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ and for beam-focusing $f_0 = 4\text{ m}$.

The properties of the reflected beam also depend on the steering angle. The ability of a RIS to steer beams with controllable steering angle is shown schematically in Figure 15(a). In Figure 15(b),(c) the power density along the beam center is presented for different steering angles. In these examples the AP orientation is fixed ($\theta_{AP} = 30^\circ$) and the AP distance from the RIS is $d_{AP} = 1\text{ m}$ in Figure 15(b) and $d_{AP} = 1.5\text{ m}$ in Figure 15(c). It is observed that, with increasing steering angle, the beam undergoes stronger diffraction, which causes its width to increase its local power density to drop, as a direct consequence of power conservation (the total beam power is preserved).

Figure 15. Impact of steering angle on beamforming (top row panels) and beam-focusing (bottom row panels). (a) Schematic representation of RIS-aided beamforming and beam-focusing. (b) Power density along the beam center for $\theta_{AP} = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ$. In (b) the AP location is characterized by $\theta_{AP} = 30^\circ$, $d_{AP} = 1 \text{ m}$ and in (c) by $\theta_{AP} = 30^\circ$, $d_{AP} = 1.5 \text{ m}$. In all examples the beam has total power $P_t = 1 \text{ W}$. For beam-forming $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ and for beam-focusing $f_0 = 4 \text{ m}$.

5.3 Hierarchical RIS-assisted, Range-Angle Localization

The ability of the RIS to focus the power of the reflected beam to a small area is ideal for localization applications. Due to the small size of the focal area, searching the entire area of interest with beam-focusing alone may require prohibitively large overhead and, therefore, searching can be assisted by hierarchical beam-tracking. The whole procedure can be split in two phases as presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Hierarchical RIS-assisted localization. (a) Phase 1: determination of user's angle with respect to the RIS, via beamforming. (b) Phase 2: determination of user's distance from the RIS via beam-focusing. In both phases, the shaded regions mark the areas where the user location is successfully identified at each hierarchical level.

In phase 1, beam-tracking is performed with beamforming through the RIS, in order to estimate the direction of the UE with respect to the RIS. In phase 2, ranging is performed with beam-focusing through the RIS, in order to estimate the distance of the UE from the RIS, along the direction identified in phase 1. With information about both the direction and the distance, the location of the UE is fully determined. Both phases follow a hierarchical and binary tree structure.

Essentially, the area of interest (e.g. the semi-infinite space in front of the RIS) is represented by a polar grid, with the RIS at its origin. In phase 1 the angular sector where the user is located is identified and in phase 2 the radial distance of the UE is estimated within the available resolution of the focal spot.

The search can be accelerated with prediction. In the absence of prediction, all levels are utilized to find the user, although the starting level may be different in each phase. However, with enough samples about the location of the UE, the AP can start predicting the next location of the user in relation to the location of the RIS and scan a small area around the predicted location using both phases but with fewer number of hierarchical levels. Prediction of the user's location in the next timeslot enables the AP to start the search from a higher hierarchical level in both phases, resulting in reduced overhead and required time to find the UE location.

5.3.1 Phase 1: Beamforming (beam-tracking)

Typically, beam-tracking is performed in the far-field, where the beam spreads as the propagation distance increases [48]. In conventional beam-tracking (without RIS), the AP scans a number of predefined directions which depends on the number of antenna elements. The number of directions to scan can be reduced significantly using a hierarchical codebook that follows the binary tree structure [49]. The hierarchical codebook is comprised of $\log_2 N$ levels, where N is the number of antenna elements. In the first level, the AP divides the area to two sectors and finds the UE in one of them. In each subsequent level, the AP divides the previous beam, where the UE was found, to two more sectors. This continues until the highest level, where the narrowest beam is reached. With this method, the number of directions to scan with exhaustive search changes from N to $2 \log_2 N$, and this difference becomes more significant with

increasing N . Because larger antenna aperture pushes the Fraunhofer distance farther, the choice for the maximum N defines also the minimum distance from the antenna where this technique can be successfully applied.

In the proposed beam-tracking framework, the same beam-tracking method is applied by the AP, where an RIS is used to steer the beam, while the signal processing remains at the AP. Unlike antenna arrays where the antenna elements are directly fed by currents, the RIS elements are excited by the incident wave of the AP. By controlling the properties of the incident wave, the excitation conditions of the RIS elements can be tuned. Therefore, the adjustment of the number of RIS elements is mainly performed by controlling the AP antenna gain and as a result, the beam-footprint on the RIS.

5.3.2 Phase 2: Beam-focusing (ranging)

With beam-focusing, most of the power is concentrated along the direction of the reflected beam. With knowledge of the angular sector where the UE is located from phase 1, the elliptical shape and controllable size of the focal area make beam-focusing ideal for hierarchical localization. This approach can be implemented as follows.

The AP through the RIS divides the angular sector from phase 1 in two distance-based sectors with beam-focusing at two large focal areas that cover more than half of the maximum distance each. The maximum distance is chosen at will and the focal areas can be chosen to overlap to avoid blind spots. After the user is found in one of those areas, the RIS divides that area in two smaller ones by adjusting the footprint size and focal distance. This process is repeated until the desired accuracy of the localization is achieved, as shown in Figure 16.

5.3.3 Angular and radial resolution

The angular resolution is determined by the minimum angular beam-width and beam-separation in phase 1 and the radial resolution is determined by the minimum size of the focal areas formed in phase 2 at each hierarchical level.

Figure 17. Example of resolution vs hierarchical level for the two phases of the hierarchical RIS-assisted localization scheme. Here, for beam-focusing in phase 2, the maximum distance is 5 m.

In phase 1, the resolution at each level depends on the 3dB (angular) width of the beam that is formed using a certain codebook. For example, the beams provided by the codebook in [50] were used to fill the levels of a new hierarchical codebook. The maximum number of hierarchical levels depends on the maximum desired angular resolution. The resulting resolution at each level of phase 1 is presented in Figure 17. In phase 2, the resolution at each level depends on the size of the focal area, and more specifically, the major radius (since it has elliptical shape). The maximum number of hierarchical levels depends on the maximum desired radial resolution (or major radius), as well as on the maximum distance that is to be scanned. For example, in the first level, the area is divided into two areas distance-wise. Assuming that the maximum distance is 5 m, the two new areas cover a 2.5 m distance each. The major radius of each area is half of the distance each area covers (see Figure 16), meaning 1.25 m each. For each subsequent level, the number of focal areas is doubled, and the major radius of each area is halved. If the maximum distance is doubled, the major radius at each level is doubled and one more codebook level is required to reach the same resolution as previously. The resolution at each level of phase 2 is presented in Figure 17.

The highest hierarchical level defines the maximum number of areas (direction-wise or distance-wise) that are scanned to find the user with the desired resolution. As the approach is binary-tree structured, in each hierarchical level two areas are scanned. Therefore, Figure 16 implies that there is a trade-off between how fast the UE location is to be determined and with what accuracy: finer resolution requires higher hierarchical levels, i.e. additional steps in the binary search procedure.

6 Sensing in Cellular Networks

6.1 Introduction

Majority of the published work on ISAC assumes monostatic sensing, i.e. the transmitter and the sensing receiver are co-located. The co-location of the receiver with the transmitter creates a self-interference (SI) problem where the transmitted signal may couple directly to the receiver. If the SI is not efficiently suppressed, it can block the sensing capability completely and, in extreme case, even damage the receiver. When compared with in-band full-duplex communications, the SI suppression in monostatic ISAC faces an additional problem, the separation of the harmful SI from the desired responses from the objects the ISAC system tries to detect, identify and localize. The SI problem in ISAC can be circumvented with bi-static, or multi-anchor sensing where transmitters and sensing receivers are in separate locations. Furthermore, the utilization of bi-static sensing allows gradual introduction of sensing to cellular networks. In the simplest case, the bi-static sensing requires no or minor changes to the existing cellular hardware and pilot or reference signals of current wireless networks already allow the sensing of the environment and detection of possible targets. However, the increase in the sensing performance without degrading the communications performance below acceptable levels will require introduction of new signals and transmission strategies as well as signal processing techniques for future ISAC systems.

Operational environments of cellular networks, especially urban environments, place severe requirements for ISAC systems. Many of the proposed ISAC use cases require the detection of objects with relatively small radar cross section (RCS) such as humans or animals as listed in, e.g. [51]. In rich scattering environments the detection of objects with small RCS is a challenging task due to strong clutter signals. These problems are addressed in this section.

6.2 System Model

The system considered in this section consists of a base station (BS), a user equipment (UE) and a target as illustrated in Figure 18 **Error! Reference source not found.**. In sensing, the BS transmits a sensing signal. The UE serves as a sensing receiver and tries to detect and localize the target in urban environment. During the sensing, the BS and UE are assumed to be static, and their location is assumed to be known. Line-of-sight (LoS) channels between the BS and the target, and the target and UE are assumed to exist. In this case, the signal reflected by the target and received at the UE before any processing can be written as

$$\mathbf{y}_0(t) = \mathbf{a}_{\text{rx}}(\theta_{\text{rx,T}})h_{\text{T,rx}}(t)\varrho(t)h_{\text{tx,T}}(t)\mathbf{a}_{\text{tx}}^{\text{H}}(\phi_{\text{tx,T}})\mathbf{v}s(t - \tau_0),$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{\text{rx}}(\theta_{\text{rx,T}})$ and $\mathbf{a}_{\text{tx}}^{\text{H}}(\phi_{\text{tx,T}})$ are array propagation vectors to the directions of the target $\theta_{\text{rx,T}}$ and $\phi_{\text{tx,T}}$ at the receiver and the transmitter, respectively. LoS channels between the transmitter and the target, and the target and the receiver are given as complex multipliers $h_{\text{tx,T}}(t)$ and $h_{\text{T,rx}}(t)$, respectively. The transmitted signal $s(t)$ is multiplied with a beamforming or pre-coding vector \mathbf{v} and received at the UE after the propagation delay τ_0 . The target $\varrho(t)$ is defined as

$$\varrho(t) = \sum_{g=1}^G \sqrt{\rho_g(t)} e^{j \cos(2\pi f_g t + \varphi_g)},$$

where G , ρ_g , f_g , and φ_g are the number of distinct scattering centres of the target, and the radar cross section, the micro-Doppler frequency and a random phase shift related to the scattering centre g , respectively. The above model allows to model the features and behaviour of targets beyond the simple detection of the target presence and its localization. This is important especially in cluttered environments where target signatures need to be separated from interfering reflections from the environment.

Figure 18. Bi-static sensing in cluttered environment.

Signal components received via other propagation paths than the target link form the clutter signal for the sensing and can be written as

$$\mathbf{y}_1(t) = \sum_{i=1}^Q \mathbf{a}_{\text{rx}}(\theta_i) h_i \mathbf{a}_{\text{tx}}^H(\phi_i) \mathbf{v}_s(t - \tau_i),$$

where terms are defined similarly to the target signal. The signal arriving at the receiver is then the sum of the signal received from the target, the clutter and the additive noise:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{y}_0(t) + \mathbf{y}_1(t) + \mathbf{n}(t),$$

where $\mathbf{n}(t)$ is the noise component.

6.3 Propagation Loss and Dynamic Range Problem

One severe problem in ISAC systems is the weak signal power a sensing node can receive from a target. The target in urban environment can have much smaller radar cross section than other objects in the environment that cause clutter reflections (e.g., a building vs. a person). Additionally, if in bi-static sensing there is a line-of-sight component from the transmitter to the

receiver, the signal received through this link can have much larger power than the signal received from the target. To illustrate this, consider the received signal power via the LoS link given by

$$P_{rx,LoS} = P_{tx} + G_{tx}(\theta_{LoS}) + G_{rx}(\phi_{LoS}) - \mathcal{L}_{LoS},$$

where P_{tx} , $G_{tx}(\theta_{LoS})$ and $G_{rx}(\phi_{LoS})$ are the transmit power fed to the antenna array, and the transmit and receive antenna gains towards the angles inside the brackets, respectively, and the propagation loss is given with \mathcal{L}_{LoS} . Antenna gains include both the array gain as well as the gain of the array elements. The signal power received from the target is given as

$$P_{rx,sens} = P_{tx} + G_{tx}(\theta_T) + G_{rx}(\phi_T) - \mathcal{L}_{tx \rightarrow T} - \mathcal{L}_{T \rightarrow rx} + 10 \log_{10} \rho,$$

where $G_{tx}(\theta_T)$ and $G_{rx}(\phi_T)$ are the antenna gains from the transmitter and the receiver towards the target, respectively. The propagation losses from the transmitter to the target and from the target to the receiver are given by $\mathcal{L}_{tx \rightarrow T}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{T \rightarrow rx}$, respectively, and ρ is the radar cross section of the target. As a simple example, if the line-of-sight link between the transmitter and the receiver is 40 meters, the propagation loss between them at the frequency of 28 GHz is 93 dB assuming a free space channel. In a case where a target with the radar cross section of 1 m² is 20 meters from both the transmitter and the receiver, the propagation loss would be 174 dB assuming free space channels exist from the target to both the transmitter and the receiver. In this case the signal from the target suffers the loss of 81 dB larger than the signal through the line-of-sight channel making the sensing very difficult. Although this is a very simplistic example, it does illustrate the dynamic range problem. The problem has been previously addressed and solution with using windowing in beamforming has been considered in [52]. Results in [52] suggest that while the beamforming with windowing can be used to alleviate the dynamic range problem, they allow sensing only at short distances. To enable ISAC sensing in outdoor urban environments more efficient methods to handle the problem caused by the clutter are needed.

6.4 Detection and Parameter Estimation in Cluttered Environments

This section explores initial solutions for the target detection and parameter estimation in cluttered urban environments. In the considered cases the detection of the target and subsequent estimation of parameters such as the direction of the target from the receiver as well as from the transmitter, and the micro-Doppler frequency ($\theta_{rx,T}$, $\phi_{tx,T}$ and f_g in the signal models) utilizes the change in received signals due to the movement of the target.

In the first case the environment is scanned before a target enters the area (step 1). The clutter due to the static objects, such as buildings, can be suppressed by subtracting the signal received at step 1 from the signal received when the target is present. After the subtraction, the signal consists of the target response, noise and the effect of measurement errors. The numerical examples presented below use only one scan of the environment in step 1, but the same principle can be used in a case where the environment has been scanned over longer period of the time to improve the model of the environment. The angle-of-arrival (AoA) and angle-of-departure (AoD) estimation in following examples are estimated with simple beam scans. More efficient and

accurate methods can be considered in the later phases of the work. In the first case only one AoA and AoD value is searched, and the angle estimates are the values that give the maximum received power.

Micro-Doppler frequency estimation can be done from the signal conditioned with the AoA and DoA estimates $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\phi}$, i.e. from

$$\mathbf{y}(\hat{\theta}, \hat{\phi}) = \mathbf{w}(\hat{\theta})^H \mathbf{Y}(\hat{\phi}),$$

by detecting the peaks in the periodogram

$$\mathcal{P} = |\mathcal{F}\{\arg(\mathbf{y}(\hat{\theta}, \hat{\phi}))\}|^2,$$

where \arg and \mathcal{F} represent the angle and Fourier transform of the vectors in brackets and the matrix $\mathbf{Y}(\hat{\phi})$ consists of signal vectors from AoA angle $\hat{\phi}$ received during the transmissions of the sensing sequence.

In the second case, the target is already in the area when the scanning starts. When the target changes place between scanning instants, received signals at the previous and current times can be used to detect and localize its location. The process of utilizing the variation in the location of the target in the detection and localization is illustrated in Figure 19. The starting point of the sensing process is shown in the left part of the figure where the transmitter and receiver are marked with black circles, blue circles represent reflecting objects in the environment causing interfering clutter, and the target is marked with the red circle. In the first step at time t , the system scans the environment, and the receiver stores received signal. At time $t + \Delta t$, the transmitter – receiver pair repeats the scan and subtracts the signals received time t from the signals at time $t + \Delta t$. The signal after the subtraction includes the information about the target at both time instants and can determine two locations for the target. However, at time $t + \Delta t$ the system cannot determine which of the two locations represent the current and which one the previous time. To combine location estimates with correct time instants, a third measurement is needed (red circle at $t + 2\Delta t$ in Figure 19).

Figure 19. Target detection and localization aided with target movement.

6.5 Numerical Examples

For the first case, the performance of sensing has been studied with simulations. The BS and the UE have been in the locations shown with the red circle and the blue cross shown in Figure 20, respectively. The target is placed randomly in the environment. The black asterisks show the example locations of the target in simulations. The performance results are averaged over the target locations. The clutter in simulations is static and is defined with AoDs at the transmitter, AoAs in the receiver, path losses and propagation delays as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 20. System geometry example.

Preliminary results are shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22. In simulations, a known signal of length 1000 symbols is transmitted repeatedly towards the target at the centre frequency of 28 GHz and with the bandwidth of 10 MHz. The receiver scans the AoA range from 0 to 90 degrees with 1 degree steps and stores the received power for each direction. At the end of the scan, the receiver detects the AoA by selecting the angle with the highest received power. In this simulation, the AoD is not estimated but the transmit beam is directed towards the target to reduce the simulation time. In a real environment the transmitter is also required to participate in the finding of the target. Simulations including the AoD estimation for the transmitter are planned to be performed in the later phase of the work. Two antenna arrays are used in simulations, a uniform linear array (ULA) with 64 elements and a uniform planar array (UPA) of size 8 x 8 elements. The target is modelled as a single reflector ($G=1$). Targets with a constant and variable RCS have been used. The constant RCS has been 1 m^2 , and the variable RCS is exponentially distributed with the average value of 1 m^2 . The micro-Doppler frequency in simulations has been defined as a random value uniformly distributed between 0 and $0.4/T_s$ (T_s = sample time). This is not a realistic value for real world cases since, e.g. in a case where the target would be a human, the micro-Doppler frequency is in the order of 1 Hz. However, the values used in the simulations are selected to shorten simulation times when assessing the operation of the micro-Doppler estimation performance. The clutter channel parameters are given in Table 1. They are extracted from the CDL-D channel model in [53]. The values in the 'Loss' row are relative to the average path loss between the BS and the UE, i.e. for each path the total path loss is the free

space loss between the BS and UE added with the value in the 'Loss' row. The path delay for each path is calculated as the product of the value in the 'Delay' row and delay spread of 100 ns added with the propagation delay related to the distance between the BS and the UE.

Table 1. Clutter channel parameters.

AoA	-180	-180	89.2	89.2	89.2	163	163	163	-137	74.5	127.7	-119.6	-9.1	-83.8
AoD	0	0	89.2	89.2	89.2	13	13	13	34.6	-64.5	-32.9	52.6	-132.1	77.2
Loss	0.2	13.5	18.8	21	22.8	17.9	20.1	21.9	22.9	27.8	23.6	24.8	30	27.7
Delay	0	0	0.035	0.612	1.363	1.405	1.804	2.596	1.775	4.042	7.937	9.424	9.708	12.525

Figure 21. AoA estimation.

Figure 22. Micro-Doppler estimation.

The signal model, system geometry and channel models in the simulations of the second case are the same as in the first one. The simulation in this case includes also the estimation of the AoD. When both the AoA and AoD search are included in the simulations, simulation times increases vastly. Simulations for the AoA and AoD estimation in this case are ongoing and will be reported later. A snapshot of the simulations is given in Figure 23 where the two peaks represent the AoA and AoD values at times t and $t + \Delta t$. This shows that the proposed method is able to find the directions of the target from both the transmitter and the receiver in a cluttered environment, but the performance assessment requires more extensive simulations.

Figure 23. An example showing the sensing results at times t and $t+\Delta t$.

6.6 Discussion on the Sensing in Cluttered Environments

Bi-static sensing is a viable option for implementing ISAC systems in urban areas. However, the rich scattering environment with the power imbalance between the target link and the link between the BS and the UE impose strict requirements for the transmission of sensing signals as well as for the techniques used to process the received signal for the detection, localization and identification of targets. Two methods were introduced in this section and preliminary simulations to assess their viability and performance have been performed but longer simulations are needed to verify their usability.

The AoA, AoD and micro-Doppler estimations used so far have been simple ones: beam scan and periodogram-based. In the later phase of the project, more efficient techniques will be explored to improve the performance.

7 Multistatic Cell-Free Massive MIMO ISAC: Performance Analysis and Power Allocation

In this part of the work, a cell-free massive (CF) MIMO-ISAC system with maximum-ratio downlink transmission schemes combined with multistatic radar-type sensing is considered. The focus lies on deriving closed-form expressions for the achievable communications rate and the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB), which serve as performance metrics for communications and sensing operations, respectively. The expressions enable to investigate important operational characteristics of multistatic cell-free massive MIMO-ISAC, including the mutual effects of communications and sensing as well as the advantages stemming from using a very large and distributed antenna array for each functionality. Furthermore, the power allocation among the access points is optimized to maximize the communications rate while guaranteeing the CRLB constraints and total transmit power budget. Extensive numerical results will be presented to validate theoretical analyses and demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed power allocation approach.

The considered system is a multistatic CF massive MIMO ISAC system, including L access points (APs), K single-antenna communications user equipments (UEs), and a sensed target. Each AP is equipped with N_t transmit and N_r receive antennas. The APs transmit probing signals to the target at a given angle of interest and data signals to the UEs at the same time and frequency. The key results obtained so far are the closed form expressions for the achievable rate and the CRLB. The expression for the achievable rate is

$$R_k(\Psi) = \bar{r} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{N_t^2 (\xi_k^T)}{N_t \sum_{j=1}^K (\bar{\mathbf{y}}_j^T \mathbf{D}_{kj}^{\beta\xi} \bar{\mathbf{y}}_j + \bar{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_j^T \mathbf{D}_k^\beta \bar{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_j) + \sigma_c^2} \right)$$

where $\xi_k = [\xi_{k1}, \dots, \xi_{kL}]^T$ includes the channel estimate variances, given as

$$\xi_{kl} = \frac{\tau_p \rho_p \beta_{kl}^2}{\tau_p \rho_p \sum_{j=1}^K \beta_{jl} |\boldsymbol{\psi}_{jl}^H \boldsymbol{\psi}_{kl}|^2 + \sigma_c^2},$$

where β_{kl} is the large-scale fading coefficient between user k and AP l ; $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{kl}$ is the pilot sequence from user k to AP l ; τ_p and ρ_p are the length of the pilot sequence and average power of the training symbols. Furthermore, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_k = [\sqrt{\gamma_{k1}}, \dots, \sqrt{\gamma_{kL}}]^T$, where γ_{kl} are the power for coefficients allocated to user k by AP l , $\mathbf{D}_{kj}^{\beta\xi} = \text{diag}\{\beta_{k1}\xi_{j1}, \dots, \beta_{kL}\xi_{jL}\}$ and $\mathbf{D}_k^\beta = \text{diag}\{\beta_{k1}, \dots, \beta_{kL}\}$. All power coefficients for communications and sensing are denoted with $\Psi = \{\{\gamma_{kl}\}_{k=1, l=1}^{K,L}, \{\eta_{kl}\}_{k=1, l=1}^{K,L}\}$.

The expression for the CRLB is

$$\text{CRLB}_p^\theta(\Psi) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_s \tau_p(\Psi)}{\tilde{\tau}_p(\Psi) \tau_p(\Psi) - |\hat{\tau}_p(\Psi)|^2},$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_s \triangleq \frac{\sigma_s^2}{2T}$, $\tau_p(\Psi) \triangleq \text{trace}(\mathbf{B}_{pp} \mathbf{R}_x \mathbf{B}_{pp}^H)$, $\tilde{\tau}_p(\Psi) \triangleq \text{trace}(\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{pp} \mathbf{R}_x \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{pp}^H)$, $\hat{\tau}_p(\Psi) \triangleq \text{trace}(\mathbf{B}_{pp} \mathbf{R}_x \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{pp}^H)$, $\dot{\mathbf{B}}_p \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{lp} (\mathbf{b}_p \mathbf{a}_l^H + \delta_{lp} \mathbf{b}_p \dot{\mathbf{a}}_l^H) \mathbf{D}_p$, $[\mathbf{R}_x]_{lp} \triangleq \delta_{lp} \xi_p^T \boldsymbol{\gamma}_p \mathbf{I}_{N_t} + \bar{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_p^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_l \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{lp}$. Here, $[\mathbf{R}_x]_{lp}$ is the submatrix of the correlation matrix \mathbf{R}_x of the transmitted signal containing entries on rows $[(l-1)N_t + 1, lN_t]$ and columns $[(p-1)N_t + 1, pN_t]$, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{lp} \triangleq \mathbf{a}_l \mathbf{a}_p^H$ and $\delta_{lp} = 1$ if $l = p$, otherwise $\delta_{lp} = 0$. Here, \mathbf{a}_l and \mathbf{b}_l are the transmit and receive steering vector at AP l .

Figure 24. Rate obtained by closed-form and Monte-Carlo simulations for $L = \{16, 32\}$, $K = 4$, $N_t = 4$, $N_r = 2$, $\tau_p = 10$, $\tau_c = 100$. It is observed that: (1) The theoretical and simulation results align well with each other, and (2) the communications sum rate increases with SNR and the larger number of APs leads to a larger sum rate in the considered cell-free massive MIMO system.

Figure 25. CRLB obtained by closed-form and Monte-Carlo simulations with $L = \{16, 32\}$, $K = 4$, $N_t = 4$, $N_r = 2$. It is observed that: (1) The theoretical and simulation results match well, (2) the CRLB decreases with SNR, and (3) the larger number of APs lead to a better sensing performance.

The work on this topic will continue during the project. The dependence of the ISAC performance on system parameters such as the number of antennas and access points will be analyzed. The cell-free massive MIMO and co-located massive MIMO ISAC systems are planned to be compared.

Furthermore, the optimization of the power allocation among access points is one of the potential study items.

8 RIS-as-a-Sensor

RIS can offer numerous advantages that contribute to enhanced network capabilities. RIS has demonstrated the ability to significantly improve overall network performance by dynamically controlling the wireless propagation environment [54]. This includes optimizing signal paths to ensure more efficient data transmission, which leads to better user experiences through increased data rates, reduced latency, and higher overall spectral efficiency. In addition to improving the capacity and reliability of wireless networks, RIS can enhance the quality of communication services, making networks more adaptable and resilient to changing conditions.

Moving towards an ISAC perspective, RIS technology also brings substantial benefits, particularly in localization and positioning applications. By functioning as an additional, controllable, and customizable anchor point, RIS enhances the accuracy of localization services [55]. This means it can significantly improve the precision of tracking and localizing connected devices [56], which is especially valuable in the development of location-based services such as navigation, asset tracking, etc. Moreover, the reflected paths it provides can be leveraged to reach NLoS areas to perform sensing.

Moreover, RIS technology is evolving beyond its original scope of merely providing controllable reflected signal paths. Recent advancements have led to slight modifications in RIS hardware, enabling them to serve not only as channel optimizers but also as passive sensors [57], [58]. This dual-purpose functionality transforms RIS into a versatile tool that simultaneously optimizes the communication channel and gathers environmental data, acting as a form of “sixth sense” for the network. This additional sensing capability can be harnessed for a variety of applications, including environmental monitoring, object detection, etc., offering a cost-effective solution for expanding network functionalities and a more efficient resource management, while creating opportunities for novel applications that require real-time data collection and processing.

8.1 Self-configuring RIS

Leveraging sensing capabilities at the RIS, and in line with the sense to communicate paradigm, we introduce the concept of self-configuring RIS, which is designed to autonomously reconfigure without relying on a dedicated control channel between the RIS controller and the network, to enhance communication performance in multi-user scenarios [58]. Without an explicit control channel between the RIS and the network, the RIS configuration is based solely on local CSI, which is obtained through a channel estimation procedure directly at the RIS. This procedure provides sufficient information on the BS-RIS and RIS-UE channels to enable self-configuration. In doing so, the RIS establishes additional high-gain reflected paths between the BS and UEs, improving overall end-to-end channel conditions. These additional paths can be detected by standard channel sounding techniques used by the BS and UEs, thus enhancing communication performance without modifications to the network infrastructure.

Figure 26. Hybrid RIS (HRIS) architecture with power detection and EH enabling self-configuration and energy harvesting, [58].

To enable sensing capabilities at the RIS, we consider a hardware architecture consisting of an array of hybrid meta-atoms that can simultaneously reflect and absorb (sense) incident signals. Each RIS element is coupled with a sampling waveguide that channels the absorbed signal through an RF circuit. This circuit, comprising RF combiners, aggregates the sensed signals from each RIS element and feeds them into a power detector to enable power sensing.

In addition to the need for CSI for configuring reflections for communication purposes, and despite their anticipated low power consumption, RIS still require a robust power distribution system to meet the energy demands of the hardware. Hence, in the proposed architecture, we place an Energy Harvesting (EH) module to perform energy harvesting, allowing us to leverage the RIS sensing capabilities not only for communication, but also for maximizing the absorbed energy in order to maintain the RIS device operational without the need for external power supplies [58].

We dub this solution as ARES: Autonomous RIS with EH and Self-configuration, which represents the first fully autonomous RIS solution, both in terms of control and energy supply. This autonomy allows for the seamless installation of RIS devices across the service area without requiring modifications to the existing network infrastructure or power distribution systems, paving the way for practical, large-scale deployment of intelligent surfaces.

8.2 Methodology

We leverage the innovative HRIS hardware architecture, which comprises two branches: a reflection branch and an absorption branch. Each element of the RIS is equipped with directional couplers that split the incoming signal, routing a fraction η for reflection and the remaining fraction $1 - \eta$ for absorption.

Figure 27. Detail on the RF hardware of the proposed RIS, [58].

The absorbed portion is processed through an RF circuit, which directs it either to a power detector or an energy harvesting module. Both branches have independently tunable phase shift banks: the reflection branch allows for adjustment of the reflection beam pattern, while the absorption branch enables the RIS to focus its absorption capabilities at specific directions as depicted in Figure 27.

Figure 28. Operational phases, [58].

To configure the RIS, we propose a codebook-based approach that estimates the AoA and computes the RIS configuration locally. This approach operates in two modes: probing and communication and EH mode, see Figure 28. In probing mode, the RIS absorption branch sweeps across all codewords in the codebook, scanning the 3D space to detect network devices and build a power profile. This power profile allows the RIS to estimate the AoAs of transmitting devices (BS and UEs). After the probing phase, the RIS enters the communication phase, optimizing its reflection branch configuration to assist data transmission between the BS and active UEs and absorption branch to maximize the harvested energy.

More in detail, during the probing mode the RIS autonomously performs directional power sensing, constructing a power profile that reveals the AoA of signals from communicating devices (see Figure 29). This operation is done through sweeping the absorption branch configuration over a codebook $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{c}_1, \dots, \mathbf{c}_L\}$ of directional codewords, corresponding to the configuration $\Theta_l = \text{diag}(\mathbf{c}_l^H)$ at the RIS, and measuring the power at the power detector. This information is then used to build a directional power profile, as depicted in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Power profile example, [57].

Power peaks correspond to the AoA of transmitting devices and provide sufficient information to retrieve the CSI of the RIS-BS and RIS-UE channels [58]. This CSI is exploited for both communication and EH. In particular, our method first optimizes the RIS configuration to maximize the gain of the reflected paths between the BS and UEs. Next, we derive a closed-form expression linking this reflection configuration to the RIS array response vectors, which maximize the absorbed power from both the BS and UEs. We demonstrate that maximizing the sensed power depends only on the RIS array response vectors directed towards the AoA from the BS and UEs, allowing this process to be performed fully locally at the RIS without reliance on the BS precoding vector. The reflection branch is optimized accordingly to maximize the reflected path gain, supporting communication between the BS and UEs. Simultaneously, the absorption branch is configured to focus on the sensed AoA directions, maximizing the harvested energy. The collected energy is stored in a rechargeable battery that powers the RIS hardware, enabling fully autonomous operation.

8.3 Results and Outcomes

To evaluate the performance and feasibility of the self-configuring RIS, we consider a square service area with a single BS and a single RIS positioned at the midpoint of adjacent edges. UEs are uniformly distributed across the area, and we compare the performance of our self-configuration scheme with the centralized approach proposed in [59], which jointly optimizes the RIS configuration and BS precoder assuming perfect CSI availability.

Figure 30. Average sum-rate achieved with self-configuration compared with a SotA centralized approach, [58].

The average sum-rate achievable in comparison with a centralized approach is shown in Figure 30, which depicts the sum-rate performance of the proposed self-configuration scheme in comparison to the centralized approach in [59], denoted with SotA, against different numbers of UEs K and different service area sizes A . This result demonstrates the feasibility of self-configuration leveraging only sensed information at the RIS, while achieving near-optimal sum-rate performance when compared to fully CSI-aware benchmarks that rely on a dedicated control channel.

Figure 31. Average harvested and consumed power against number of HRIS elements N , different values of traffic ζ , unit cells pin diodes power consumption P_{ON} and quantization level Q , [58].

Furthermore, we assess the energy harvesting performance by comparing the harvested and consumed power of the RIS. Results are shown in Figure 31, against different configurations of the RIS hardware both in terms of quantization level of the phase shifters, and power consumed by the unit cell, against different levels of traffic in the network, indicated with ζ . Results show that the harvested power is comparable with the consumed one, demonstrating the feasibility of EH optimization leveraging sensing.

Figure 32. LoC probability against battery capacity, [58].

Finally, we evaluate the charge and discharge performance of the battery powering the autonomous HRIS, modeled using an irreducible Markov Chain. This statistical model allows us to estimate the lifespan of the HRIS by calculating the probability of entering a low battery charge state, defined as when the available energy falls below a threshold Γ , the minimum required to operate the HRIS. When the battery charge drops below the threshold, the system enters a loss of charge (LoC) state. Figure 32 depicts the LoC probability as a function of battery size, showing that as the battery size increases, the likelihood of entering the LoC state decreases, extending the operational lifespan of the HRIS.

8.4 Discussion

The contribution demonstrates the feasibility of leveraging sensed information at the RIS in a sense to communicate manner, where RIS configuration is automatically optimized based only on local information thus removing control overhead and optimizing network resources. Information gathered at the RIS could also be further leveraged to locate active users in the network by extracting AoA information and processing it. Hence, finding a good fit in technological enablers for ISAC. Further activities might include leveraging information available at the RIS to enable novel localization techniques, enhance tracking and positioning of connected devices, and integrate sensor fusion methods for greater accuracy and reliability.

9 Mutual Coupling-aware Optimization of Conformal RIS Layouts

The rise of RIS in modern wireless systems offers new possibilities by dynamically manipulating EM wave propagation, with benefits such as flexibility, low cost, and energy efficiency. This positions RIS as a key technology for 6G, enabling channel optimization for diverse applications [54]. While most implementations focus on planar RIS, conformal surfaces in RIS technology are designed to adapt to the specific shape and topography of their deployment environment, providing greater flexibility and performance compared to traditional flat-panel designs [60].

Figure 33. Reflection properties of curved surfaces (a) planar, (b) cylindrical and super-cylindrical (c), [61].

These surfaces can be molded to fit curved or irregular structures, such as buildings or vehicles, enhancing their ability to manipulate EM waves in complex settings. By closely matching the surface of deployment, conformal RIS ensures optimal wave reflection and beamforming, leading to improved communication capabilities in environments where flat surfaces are either unavailable or suboptimal. Figure 33 illustrates the differing wave reflections of flat and curved surfaces, suggesting the potential of 3D or conformal RIS.

Despite advancements in fabrication, challenges in precision unit placement on 3D surfaces remain, alongside complex mathematical modeling requirements. Optimizing 3D RIS layouts demands sophisticated algorithms to navigate these challenges and achieve performance improvements beyond planar systems.

This contribution introduces a novel approach that optimizes the arrangement of RIS elements, leveraging mutual coupling for enhanced performance [61]. The approach is suitable for the optimization of large RIS deployments that has to cope with irregular deployment structures, moreover, as it considers the mutual coupling effect, it is also suitable for the layout optimization of holographic RIS with inter-element spacing below the $\lambda/2$ limit.

9.1 Methodology

When analyzing the electromagnetic properties of antenna arrays with arbitrary shapes (including RIS), accurate channel modeling is essential to capture the interaction between signals and antennas. Conventional RIS channel models often fail to meet this requirement, as most do not account for mutual coupling. Mutual coupling is an effect that occurs when antennas are closely spaced, causing the electromagnetic properties of one element to be influenced by its neighbors. Moving from planar to non-planar structures can reduce the inter-element distance, leading to stronger mutual coupling. To address this, we assume a channel model $H(\mathbf{Q})$, which depends on the 3D positions of the RIS elements, represented by the matrix $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times N}$, where N is the number of elements. $H(\mathbf{Q})$ includes mutual coupling effects, such as those described in [61], [62]. It is important to note that different models accounting for mutual coupling can also be applied.

Figure 34. Schematic of the proposed approach, [61].

Figure 34 illustrates the schematic of our proposed solution, which formulates an optimization problem aimed at determining the optimized 3D location of each RIS element, \mathbf{Q} , and the configuration matrix $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$, which represents the passive beamforming and is a diagonal matrix. The inputs to this optimization are the RIS initial conditions, the mutual coupling-aware channel model, the chosen KPIs (e.g., rate, SNR, directivity, coverage area), which define the objective function to be maximized, $f(\mathbf{Q}, \Phi)$, and geometrical information about the deployment region (e.g., a 3D sphere, a cylindrical car door, or a spherical support). Based on these inputs, the optimized 3D locations of the RIS, and the inter-element spacing.

The proposed optimization framework follows two main steps. First, for an initial 3D configuration of the RIS elements $\mathbf{Q}^{(0)}$, the RIS configuration Φ is optimized based on the chosen KPIs. This step can be performed using existing state-of-the-art methods (e.g., [63]). In the second step, for a fixed RIS configuration $\Phi^{(i)}$, the 3D locations of the RIS elements are updated to maximize the KPIs while respecting the deployment region constraints, and, if applicable, the number of RIS elements and the properties of the substrate. Figure 5 shows a schematic of this step. Each element's position is updated by computing the gradient of the objective function with respect to the 3D locations, $\nabla f(\mathbf{Q}^{(i)})$, which represents the direction of maximum gain. The position is then

adjusted by adding a scaled version of this gradient to the previous location, and the new position is projected onto the feasible set to ensure compliance with the deployment constraints and RIS substrate properties, i.e., $Q^{(i+1)} = P_Q(Q^{(i)} + \alpha_i \nabla f(Q^{(i)}))$. More details on the algorithm can be found in [61].

9.2 Results and Outcomes

We evaluate the proposed approach in a scenario where the center of the RIS is positioned at the origin, serving a single-antenna BS and single antenna UE located at a distance of 1.3m and azimuth and elevation angles of 30° and 120° relative to the RIS, with the transmit signal from the BS incident from the broadside of the RIS. In our baseline configuration, we assume a total of $N = 100$ $\lambda/2$ -length dipoles forming the RIS. The initial positions, $Q^{(0)}$, of the dipoles follow a regular conformal arrangement, and we analyze four specific configurations: i) ULA with $\lambda/16$ inter-element spacing, which is chosen to keep the overall size of the ULA proportional to other initial structures, ensuring comparable average pathloss between the RIS, BS, and UE in all experiments, ii) a UPA with $\lambda/2$ inter-element spacing, iii) a cylindrical RIS with $\lambda/2$ inter-element spacing and a radius of 0.1m, and iv) a spherical RIS with $\lambda/2$ inter-element spacing and a radius of 0.1m.

For each of these configurations, we evaluate two cases: i) unconstrained and ii) constrained optimization. In the unconstrained case, the RIS elements can move freely within a 3D sphere of radius $R = 0.05$ m centered at the origin. In the constrained case, the RIS shape must maintain the overall geometry of the initial structure, reflecting practical constraints on RIS fabrication (e.g., a cylinder of a specified radius or a plane with defined dimensions). The operating frequency is set to 30GHz, i.e., $\lambda = 1$ cm.

Figure 35. Unconstrained optimization of the RIS elements layout, [61].

Figure 35 shows how the initial RIS structures can be optimally transformed within a 3D space using the proposed approach. The analysis of the four scenarios reveals that the optimized RIS elements tend to spread out along the y - and z -axis, following a regular pattern, and ii) the elements move relatively closer to the BS and UE location. This shift reduces the path loss between the RIS, BS, and UE, thus improving the SNR. To limit the impact of element position

variation, we keep the 3D sphere radius small to focus on the effects of elements displacement optimization.

Figure 36. Bar plot of the maximum SNR obtained with conventional and optimized RIS shape, [61].

From Figure 36, we observe that the optimized dipole positions notably enhance the SNR, underscoring the potential of RIS shape optimization to boost communication performance if compared to only optimizing the RIS configuration (SotA). It is also noticeable that the optimized RIS configurations exhibit periodicity, aligning with the incoming and reflected plane waves. Figure 35 also shows convergence of the proposed optimization algorithm.

Figure 37. Constrained optimization of the RIS elements layout, [61].

Figure 37 illustrates the efficacy of the proposed approach in optimizing RIS element placement within a constrained shape. As in the unconstrained case, the optimized arrangements display periodic patterns and non-uniform inter-element spacing. However, the SNR improvement is less pronounced due to the reduced flexibility in element positioning (See Figure 36).

9.3 Discussion

The proposed approach enables the optimization of the shape of the RIS constrained to specific deployment characteristics and to maximize given KPI. The proposed approach considers

mutual coupling effect, which are introduced either with irregular (non-planar) displacement of the elements of the RIS, or an inter-element distance below $\lambda/2$, making it suitable for optimizing large and holographic surfaces.

10 Hardware Impairment Mitigation for Wideband ISAC Applications

The trend in the evolution of mobile communication standards points towards an enormous expansion of the capabilities and features of the familiar cell-based system. Lately, the execution of sensing or localization tasks by static and dynamic nodes in the mobile network through RADAR-derived schemes has been a topic of interest. The dynamic at play at the moment is an integration of sensing functionality into – or an augmentation of – an existing communication system whose per-user bandwidth is currently limited by multi-channel schemes like OFDM due to the need to service a large number of end users simultaneously. This, however, constitutes a problem for the efficacy of the sensing portion of the application, because in RADAR systems the resolution is inversely proportional to the available contiguous bandwidth of the signal. With the spectrum of envisioned tasks for future ISAC applications requiring resolutions as low as on the order of millimeters, a longevity-focused approach necessitates considering wideband transceivers and their subsequent technical challenges and pitfalls.

10.1 Hardware Impairments in Wideband Communication Systems

Challenges incurred by designing a ISAC system with high-res sensing as the defining and indispensable feature are manifold, such as negating the ability to freely allocate the available resources to fit the requirements of multiple end users in the serviced region simultaneously or the higher frequency-selectivity of both the employed hardware components and the communication channel itself when increasing the bandwidth. Additionally, with increasing carrier frequency – which, in turn, is required to accommodate the higher bandwidth of the signal – the free-space attenuation increases drastically. This puts additional strain on the link budget, meaning that power loss due to suboptimal signal level management is more detrimental. Coupled with the already high Peak-to-Average-Power-Ratio (PAPR) of OFDM signals, which limits the efficacy of amplification stages in the signal chain, this results in a two-dimensional optimization problem in the frequency and time domain. While the time domain effects are beyond the scope of this contribution, the frequency domain impairments will be tackled in a two-stage approach.

10.2 Receiver Calibration Scheme

In Frequency Division Multiplexing schemes like OFDM, each subchannel is so narrow that it can be assumed to be flat without oversimplification. Rather than applying frequency-dependent equalization, each subchannel can be weighted with a real-valued scalar to sufficiently equalize the system as a whole, keeping the complexity of the transceivers low. A wideband system cannot circumvent the problem of frequency-dependent attenuation in such a fashion and must therefore mitigate the effects of imperfect components in another way. Assuming an optimally

engineered waveform with a perfectly flat spectrum, as well as good spectral and power efficiency, the subsequent challenge is presented by the imperfect transceiver hardware sending and receiving these waveforms. A calibration of the hardware components offers a considerable margin for improvement of the signal integrity and the performance of functions associated with it. It is performed by adapting a routine from fiberoptic communication systems, where the entire receiver assembly – meaning all components from the receiver frontend to the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) – is probed with a continuous wave (CW) signal from a laser source. The frequency of the probe laser is varied in arbitrarily fine, discrete steps across the bandwidth of interest, while the frequency of the local oscillator (LO) laser source remains fixed. The resulting complex beating frequency in the mixer section of the coherent receiver is processed in the digital domain to reject image frequencies and extract amplitude and phase information from it. Various sources of phase differences, known as skew and resulting from imperfectly length-matched fiber sections within a balanced photodetector (BPD) or between in-phase and quadrature component, as well as the frequency-dependent amplitude, can be identified and compensated for. The complex frequency profile resulting from the calibration procedure can then be inverted and applied to any transmitted signal in the form of a digital pre-equalization filter. At radio frequencies, the scheme is naturally quite similar, despite minor technical differences. Laser sources are replaced with electrical oscillators or arbitrary waveform generators (AWG), and no opto-electrical conversion is necessary, eliminating BPDs as a potential source for impairments. A block diagram of an adapted version of the calibration setup will be shown in a later section.

10.3 Transmitter Calibration Scheme

With a calibrated receiver chain, the transmitter can be calibrated without the need for extra equipment. Instead of a CW signal, broadband noise with a flat power spectrum is applied, allowing for a much quicker calibration procedure. Because detrimental effects of the receiver chain have been eliminated in the previous step, the remaining impairments must originate from the transmitter. The received signal spectrum can be inverted and the pre-equalization filter is updated.

While a single calibration in a laboratory setting utilizes the general-purpose measurement equipment, which is not tailored to the task at hand and therefore not optimized for speed, and while a single calibration is often enough in the highly controlled research environment, integrating such a functionality into field-appropriate hardware assemblies would require developing specialized submodules and periodically repeating the procedure to account for dynamic events, such as changes in the environmental conditions and wear and tear of the components.

10.4 Planned WP2 Experimental Work at HHI

While the calibration routine described above is not especially technologically advanced, an exploration of the possible improvements of communication and sensing capabilities, especially in a quantifiable manner, has not been undertaken so far. With task T2.3 approaching, which involves experimental work to lay the foundation for the hardware demonstrators in WP4, a measurement campaign will have to be designed to comparatively analyze the potential of the calibration procedure. The setting for these experiments will be a miniaturized radio cell developed for antenna characterization and other measurements that can be performed on a small scale before upscaling to field trials. A photo of the cell and the currently employed receiver hardware, which includes integrated THz-band mixers-plus-amplifiers and discrete baseband amplifier units is depicted in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Miniaturized radio cell setup at HHI.

A block diagram of the proposed RF receiver chain calibration setup with hardware components already available in the HHI lab is depicted in Figure 39. While the hardware demonstrators will eventually operate at 28 GHz carrier frequency, these preliminary experiments at 300 GHz can provide insights that carry over into the lower frequency bands, too.

Figure 39. RF receiver chain calibration routine block diagram.

Lastly, with the setup assembled and the calibration routine as described above, the experiments will focus on comparing communication and sensing performance with and without calibrated hardware. Transmitter and receiver units can be arranged in a monostatic or bi-static configuration (see Figure 40) and their position relative to one another can be varied with the use of a collaborative robotic arm, which is installed in the radio cell.

Figure 40. Communication and sensing experimental setup with co-located monostatic (i) and bi-static (ii) transceivers.

10.5 Conclusion

On the physical layer, characterizing and calibrating the employed hardware is a promising strategy for enabling communication and sensing beyond multi-user narrowband configurations and thereby dramatically improving data throughput and sensing resolution. Fraunhofer HHI plans to conduct experiments to quantify the achievable gain in respective performance metrics and thereby putting the ISAC enablers developed in WP2 to the test in preparation for the hardware demonstrations in WP4.

11 RIS Design for ICAS Systems

The concept of incorporating Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) into wireless communications began gaining traction in the early 2010s. RIS are employed to manipulate electromagnetic wave reflections in smart environments, thereby extending network coverage without the need to increase the number of access points, such as gNB. Additionally, with the introduction of millimeter waves (mm-waves) in 5G communications, non-line-of-sight (NLOS) propagation conditions have become more challenging. RIS can mitigate these challenges by enhancing data rates, reducing unnecessary retransmissions, and minimizing handovers caused by Radio Link Failures.

Within the scope of the project, Greenerwave have designed a millimeter-wave (FR2) reconfigurable intelligent surface based on electronically tunable pixels with binary phase modulation. Specifically, a 20 cm x 20 cm metasurface was designed to operate within the frequency range of approximately 28 GHz. This RIS comprises 1600 pixels ($M = 40$, $N = 40$), each supporting two polarizations (P_H, P_V) with binary ON/OFF states. The pixels, based on PIN diodes, achieve a phase shift close to π between states and exhibit low dissipation (< -2 dB) across a bandwidth from 25.5 GHz to 29 GHz [64].

For the sake of the design, the metasurfaces can be modeled analytically to describe their reflected radiation in all directions with respect to an incident wave, in both near and far fields. By wisely combining the states of the different pixels (PIN diodes) [out of 2^{3200} metasurface possible configurations], we can target users in different directions (azimuth/elevation) and reshape the incident wave to be reflected into beams of different widths.

11.1 Binary Phase RIS Analytical Model

The reflection of an electromagnetic wave incident on the RIS can be precisely controlled by carefully switching the PIN diodes. As demonstrated earlier, the states of these PIN diodes dictate the phase of the local reflection coefficient across the RIS. The phase distribution, φ_{nm} , where n and m number pixels in the array $m \in \{0, \dots, M - 1\}$ and $n \in \{0, \dots, N - 1\}$, is determined according to the following equation:

$$\Phi_{n,m} = \Phi_r(x_n, y_m) - \Phi_i(x_n, y_m),$$

where $\Phi_i(x_n, y_m)$ and $\Phi_r(x_n, y_m)$ are the phase distributions created by the incident and the desired reflected waves at the position x_n, y_m of the n, m -th pixel in the cartesian plane with respect to the RIS center.

Assuming that E_i is the incident wave created by the transmitting (Tx) antenna that illuminated the RIS. The radiation pattern $E_r(\theta, \varphi)$ in θ, φ directions created by the RIS set to a given pixels' binary configurations can be approximated as follows [65]:

$$E_r(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} E_i(x_n, y_m) \cdot f_{n,m}(\theta, \varphi) \cdot \Gamma_{n,m} \cdot \cos(\theta_{n,m}) \cdot \exp\left(j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)\right) \cdot [x_n \cos(\varphi) + y_m \sin(\varphi)],$$

where:

- $f_{n,m}(\theta, \varphi)$ represents the scattering pattern of each individual pixels (n, m) in the array.
- $\Gamma_{n,m}$ is the local reflection coefficient from the n, m^{th} pixel: $\Gamma_{n,m} = A_{n,m} \cdot \exp(j \cdot \Phi_{n,m})$ with $A_{n,m}$ is the reflection amplitude of the pixel and $\Phi_{n,m}$ is the reflection phase given in $\Phi_{n,m} = \Phi_r(x_n, y_m) - \Phi_i(x_n, y_m)$.
- $E_i(x_n, y_m)$ is the electric field of the incident wave at the n, m -th pixel,
- $\theta_{n,m}$ is the θ -angle at which n, m -th pixel sees the Tx antenna.

Since the RIS is composed from microstrip patched (printed circuit), we can assume that $f_{n,m}(\theta, \varphi) = \cos(\theta)$. Consequently, the above equation for the radiation pattern simplifies to the following form:

$$E_r(\theta, \varphi) = \cos(\theta) \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} E_i(x_n, y_m) \cdot A_{n,m} \exp(j \Phi_{n,m}) \cos(\theta_{n,m}) \cdot \exp\left(j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)\right) [x_n \cos(\varphi) + y_m \sin(\varphi)]$$

Figure 41: Schematics of mutual positions of the RIS, receiving (Rx) and transmitting (Tx) horn antennas in the spherical coordinates system.

We focus on two practically important examples when:

- (i) Near-field configuration, *i.e.* the Tx antenna is placed at a distance to the RIS comparable to its size D_m .
- (ii) Far-field configuration, *i.e.* the Tx antenna is far away from the RIS such that the incident wave can be considered as a plane wave. The receiving (Rx) horn antenna is at a distance $D_{RX} > \frac{2 \cdot D_m^2}{\lambda}$

11.1.1 Tx antenna is close to RIS: Near-field configuration

The first scenario resembles the configuration of a classical reflect array antenna. In this setup, the incident wave emitted by the transmitting (Tx) horn antenna is modeled as a spherical wave, while the reflected wave is approximated as a plane wave propagating towards the receiver in the spherical coordinates $\theta_{RX}, \varphi_{RX}$ [64].

$$\Phi_{n,m} = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_{RX}) [x_n \cdot \cos(\varphi_{RX}) + y_m \cdot \sin(\varphi_{RX})] + \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{(x_n - x_{TX})^2 + (y_n - y_{TX})^2 + z_{TX}^2},$$

where: $z_{TX} = D_{TX} \cdot \cos(\theta_{TX})$, $x_{TX} = D_{TX} \cdot \sin(\theta_{TX}) \cos(\varphi_{TX})$ and $y_{TX} = D_{TX} \cdot \sin(\theta_{TX}) \sin(\varphi_{TX})$.

The value of $\Phi_{n,m}$ for each n,m-th pixel was used to decide the ON/OFF state of the pixels and we will use the equation of the radiation pattern $E_r(\theta, \varphi)$ to simulate the reflected near field radiation pattern under different steering directions $\theta_{RX} = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 60° assuming $\varphi_{RX} = 0$, $D_{TX} = 145$ mm, $\theta_{TX} = 45^\circ$ and $\varphi_{TX} = 270^\circ$.

Figure 42. Near field configuration and results of the radiation pattern analytical model for different RIS configurations defined by steering directions $\theta_{RX} = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 60° ($\varphi_{RX} = 0^\circ$). [64]

From the figures presented, we note that the rule used to decide the metasurface's binary configuration allowed the RIS to achieve high directivity along the steered reflected beam direction. It proves that 2 states phase shift modulation is enough.

However, as the reflection angle increases, the directivity decreases, following the cosine antenna rule. This occurs because the effective aperture of the RIS reduces as the angle of reflection becomes more oblique, leading to diminished radiation efficiency in directions further from the normal. Consequently, higher reflection angles result in reduced directivity, which is a well-known limitation in beam-steering systems based on passive surfaces.

11.1.2 Tx antenna is far from RIS: Far-field configuration

This scenario can be assimilated to RIS used as an access point (5G gNB, WiFi AP) extender. The TX antenna is placed far from the RIS and so, both incident and reflected waves can be modeled as plane waves. The equation of the distribution of the phase of the n,m-th pixel of the RIS can be formulated as [64]:

$$\Phi_{n,m} = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_{RX}) [x_n \cdot \cos(\varphi_{RX}) + y_m \cdot \sin(\varphi_{RX})] + \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_{TX}) [x_n \cdot \cos(\varphi_{TX}) + y_m \cdot \sin(\varphi_{TX})].$$

The phase profile $\Phi_{n,m}$ exhibits a periodic profile that cannot be accurately approximated using only two-phase states. This causes imperfections in the beamforming process, leading to ghost side lobes. Ghost side lobes are undesired secondary radiation patterns that appear in unintended directions alongside the main lobe. This can be seen in the next figures with the appearance of ghost beams in $\varphi = 180^\circ$ directions. The strength of these unwanted side lobes increases when the reflection angle becomes more oblique.

Figure 43. Far field configuration and results of the radiation pattern analytical model for different RIS configurations defined by steering directions $\theta_{RX} = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 60° ($\varphi_{RX} = 0^\circ$) [64].

We are working on overcoming this problem by proposing a new RIS binary configuration optimization algorithm that reduces the side lobes in far field.

The results demonstrated that with the adopted RIS design, we successfully generated beams with a half-power beamwidth (HPBW) of 3° . By strategically configuring the pixel states, we can steer these beams in various directions relative to the receiver's position. We are developing RIS control algorithms to generate wider beams. Measurement campaigns will be conducted on the RIS to validate this analytical model.

11.2 Propagation Model Using RIS

In future 5G deployments, the RIS (Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface) will play a critical role in enhancing non-line-of-sight (NLOS) communications by providing a relay point between two line-of-sight (LOS) paths.

Let's define $d_{TX,RX}$ the distance between receiver and transmitter. Additionally, $(d_{TX,RIS}, \theta_{TX}, \varphi_{TX})$ and $(d_{RIS,RX}, \theta_{RX}, \varphi_{RX})$ represent the spherical coordinates of the transmitter and receiver relative to the RIS center, where $d_{TX,RIS}$, $d_{RIS,RX}$ are the distances between the RIS center and the TX and RX antennas, respectively.

The NLOS path loss between the transmitter and receiver can be modeled as follows [66]:

$$PL_{no_Ris} = PL(d_0) + N(f) \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_{TX,RX}}{d_0} \right) + X(f),$$

with:

- $PL(d_0)$ is the basic transmission loss at the reference distance d_0 ,
- $N(f)$ is the distance-based loss factor, which depends on the frequency f ,

- $X(f)$ represents the sum of losses due to obstacles (e.g., windows, brick walls) and the operating frequency f .

When including the RIS as a relay, the pathloss model can be expressed as the sum of two LOS pathloss models with the RIS contribution:

$$PL_{withRIS} = PL(d_0) + N(f) \left[\log_{10} \left(\frac{d_{TX,RIS}}{d_0} \right) + \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_{RIS,RX}}{d_0} \right) \right] + G_{RIS},$$

Here, G_{RIS} is expressed as:

$$G_{RIS} = G_{ill}(\theta_{TX}, \varphi_{TX}) + \eta + G_{ref}(\theta_{RX}, \varphi_{RX}, HPBW),$$

where:

- $L_{ill}(\theta_{TX}, \varphi_{TX})$ is the illumination loss of the metasurface, which depends on the direction of the incident wave. The illumination level varies across the metasurface pixels depending on their positions in the RIS.
- η represents the metasurface dissipation loss, which is influenced primarily by the PIN diode design, operating frequency, substrate loss, and heat, independent of the propagation environment.
- $G_{ref}(\theta_{RX}, \varphi_{RX}, HPBW)$ is the reflection gain due to RIS beamforming in the direction of the receiver $(\theta_{RX}, \varphi_{RX})$. This gain will decrease when the reflection angle becomes more oblique or when the reflected beams are wider.

11.3 RIS for User Tracking

Several user tracking techniques are already in use in cellular networks. These include Angle of Arrival (AoA) estimation from uplink signals, time propagation estimation during the Timing Advance procedure, and Channel State Information (CSI) reporting. These methods enable network operators to monitor users' movements and optimize network performance. In 5G, beamforming allows the gNB (gNodeB) to steer beams in various directions, and with feedback from users (e.g., PRACH, L1-RSRP, PMI), the network can achieve a more accurate understanding of channel conditions and user locations [67].

The RIS can be viewed as an extension of the base station. By implementing similar beamforming and steering mechanisms at the RIS, the gNB gains an additional source of information, enhancing the precision of environmental sensing and user tracking. Furthermore, in case of Radio Link Failures (RLF), the RIS can assist in re-establishing communication and maintaining continuous user tracking within the cell. As first tracking algorithm, we wanted to reproduce the 5G procedure of beam sweeping and refinement at the RIS and measure its performance [68].

As a preliminary tracking algorithm, we aim to replicate the 5G beam sweeping and refinement procedure at the RIS to evaluate its performance. The approach involves implementing a wide beam sweeping mechanism, akin to Synchronization Signal Block (SSB) sweeping, over time. To achieve this, we dynamically calculate the metasurface configurations to generate wide beams in different directions, covering 120° in azimuth and 120° in elevation.

Based on the User Equipment (UE) feedback – similar to SSB-index-RSRP report, which contains the index of the wide beam with the highest RSRP – the RIS will then generate configurations for narrower beams (similar to CSI-RS). These narrower beams are swept within the region of the best identified wide beam. The UE will report the index of the narrow beam with the highest RSRP, and the RIS will apply this configuration for data transmission to the UE.

Figure 44: RIS UE exchanges for beam steering and refinement.

12 Summary and Next Steps

This document reports the work and results from the first 10 months of the WP2 in the INSTINCT project. The research in WP2 has concentrated on several topics. The system and algorithm studies have been performed on the use of multi-carrier waveforms in multi-sensor ISAC systems, on solving challenges in positioning applications, and on the system and algorithm development for sensing in cellular as well as in cell-free networks. Furthermore, the use of RISs in sensing and their implementation is under active work and first results of the RIS development for ISAC systems is reported in this deliverable. One important topic in the project is to understand the effect of hardware imperfections on both the communications and sensing performance in ISAC systems and develop methods for impairment mitigation.

The work on the topics described in this document continues in the WP2 throughout the project. The results will be reported in research literature and in upcoming deliverables: *D2.2: Final report on joint communications and sensing enablers* (at the end of 2025), *D2.3: Final report on holographic surfaces for JCAS* (summer 2026), and *D2.4: Final report on the co-design of sensing and communications* (summer 2026).

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